

interstore

D5.3 – Report on evaluation of use cases and KPIs evaluation

WP5 - Pilots Demonstration

T5.2 - Residential Flexibility pilot

T5.3 - Commercial Flexibility pilot

T5.4 - E-Mobility Flexibility pilot

T5.5 - Industrial Flexibility pilot

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ATS	Automatic Transfer Switch
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BESS	Battery energy storage system
BMS	Battery Management System
BSP	Balancing Service Provider
CHP	Combined heat and power
CHAdEMO	CHArge de MOve (EV charging standard)
DERs	Distributed energy resources
DES	Distributed energy storage
DSO	Distribution system operator
E2E	End-to-end
EMS	Energy management system
EV	Electric vehicle
FCC	Full Communication Chain
FCR	Frequency Containment Reserve
FFR	Fast Frequency Response
FPS	Fast peak shaving
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich
GFM	Grid Forming
GFL	Grid Following
HEMS	Hybrid energy management systems
HESS	Hybrid energy storage systems
HP	Heat Pump
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
KPIs	Key performance indicators
LPC	Legacy Protocol Converter
mFRR	Manual Frequency Restoration Reserves
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NATS	Neural Autonomic Transport System
PC	Personal computer
POI	Point of interconnection
PQ	Power Quality
PV	Photovoltaic system
RPi	Raspberry Pi
UC	Use case
UCAP	Ultracapacitor
SBC	Single board computer
SoC	State of Charge
SoF	State of Function
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TES	Thermal storage
TSO	Transmission system operator
UPS	Uninterruptible power supply
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
VI	Virtual inertia
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
VRFB	Vanadium redox flow battery

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme, the InterSTORE project supports Europe's transition towards a decentralised, renewable-driven energy system. It does this by demonstrating the interoperability of distributed energy resources (DERs) and storage technologies across five pilot sites: Germany, Austria, Italy, Portugal and Spain. Based on the integration and testing activities detailed in Deliverable D5.2 [1], [2], this deliverable (D5.3) evaluates the performance of the deployed solutions in the demonstrations by assessing the use cases against the key performance indicators (KPIs) and targets outlined in Deliverable D5.1 [1], [3].

The main objectives of this deliverable are:

- 1) To evaluate the technical, operational and economic performance of the InterSTORE solutions as demonstrated in the pilot sites.
- 2) To assess each use case against the KPI framework established in D5.1 [3], enabling quantitative and qualitative benchmarking and targets defined.
- 3) To derive and report lessons learned across the pilots, highlighting the strengths, challenges and potential for replication of the developed integrations and software tools.

Each pilot site focused on a set of use cases that were tailored to their local context, assets and stakeholder needs. Key highlights include:

Austria (CyberGrid): Deployment in residential energy communities, showcasing multi-device integration, user-centric energy management and the scalability of the legacy protocol converter (LPC, [4])-based communication framework.

Germany (Forschungszentrum Jülich, FZJ): Demonstrating the integrated control of battery energy storage systems (BESS), photovoltaic (PV) systems, and heat pumps (HP), with an emphasis on efficiency, interoperability, and grid support functionalities.

Italy (Enel X): Validation of flexibility services using various assets, such as PV, batteries and electric vehicle (EV) chargers, and their integration into an energy management system (EMS) for system operators and market platforms.

Portugal (Capwatt): Industrial-scale testing of second-life batteries and new energy storage system (ESS) installations to support EV charging simultaneity factor. Explore EV users demand response and optimal HESS operation.

Spain (HESStec): Validation of hybrid energy storage systems (batteries and ultracapacitors) for advanced grid services, such as black start, fast frequency response, and firming services.

The KPI evaluation confirmed that InterSTORE technologies enable the effective monitoring, control and integration of heterogeneous DERs. Across the pilots, interoperability was demonstrated with the IEEE 2030.5 protocol over NATS and LPC successfully bridging legacy (i.e., MQTT and Modbus) and modern communication standards (i.e., IEEE 2030.5). Performance improvements were observed in terms of the flexibility, resilience and reliability of integrated assets and their EMS. The replicability of the deployments was proven in diverse regulatory, technical and market contexts. Lessons learned provided valuable insights into areas such as protocol harmonisation, latency management, cybersecurity and user acceptance.

Overall, the pilots confirmed the proposed project KERs and that the InterSTORE framework can integrate distributed energy resources (DERs) and storage systems in a scalable and secure way, which will contribute to the flexibility and stability of future European grids.

This deliverable presents an evaluation of KPIs that provides quantitative evidence of the value created by InterSTORE. These results will inform future exploitation, replication and policy recommendations, ensuring that the project's outcomes accelerate the transition to a decentralised, decarbonised energy system and support market adoption.

It is worth noting that, according to the FAIR principle and the data management plan procedures of the InterSTORE project, this deliverable will be uploaded to the Zenodo repository [5], together with material useful for analysing the KPIs. This includes an Excel file summarising the information for each KPI, as well as a list of documents and files that can be used to recalculate the KPIs (*'proofs'*).

1 Introduction

Europe's energy transition requires the large-scale deployment of renewable energy, as well as new mechanisms to manage the variability, decentralisation and complexity of the emerging system. Distributed energy resources (DERs), including storage systems, photovoltaic generation, electric vehicles and controllable loads, can provide the flexibility needed to balance supply and demand. However, their full potential can only be realised if they are integrated into interoperable EMS frameworks and evaluated against transparent performance benchmarks.

The InterSTORE project addresses this challenge by developing and demonstrating solutions that ensure the interoperability, scalability and reliability of managing diverse DERs across heterogeneous infrastructures. Following the integration and testing of these solutions, as reported in Deliverable D5.2 [2], the present deliverable (D5.3) focuses on evaluating their performance in real-world demonstrations. The aim is to assess the performance of the project's use cases, implemented in the Austrian, German, Italian, Portuguese and Spanish pilots, against the key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3]. This evaluation provides quantitative and qualitative insights into the effectiveness of the InterSTORE framework and its capacity to contribute to a decentralised, flexible European energy system.

Deliverable D5.1 defined the KPI framework to measure progress towards the project's objectives [3]. These indicators cover multiple dimensions, including technical performance (e.g. efficiency, interoperability and latency), operational reliability, economic value and system-level impact. Deliverable D5.2 then reported on the deployment of the InterSTORE architecture at the pilot sites, detailing the configuration of the IEEE 2030.5 protocol, the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) and the Neural Autonomic Transport System (NATS) messaging system to integrate diverse devices and platforms [2]. Based on these foundations, Deliverable D5.3 provides the first consolidated assessment of whether the solutions achieve the intended outcomes when applied to real use cases.

The evaluation methodology applied in this deliverable ensures comparability across pilot sites while respecting their specific contexts. KPIs were measured using data collected directly from the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) platforms and devices deployed in the demonstrations, complemented by qualitative feedback from pilot operators. Where appropriate, normalisation procedures were applied to harmonise results across pilots with different asset types, scales and regulatory frameworks. The assessment therefore, combines objective measurements with interpretative analysis, aiming to highlight both performance levels and lessons learned. This document is complemented by an excel file (annex) with all the rational and quantitative data to justify the reached KPI explained hereafter.

A recap of the KPI framework is included to maintain continuity with D5.1. At project level, the indicators define target values against which the pilot results can be benchmarked. A consolidated table containing all KPIs and their respective targets has been provided to facilitate the interpretation of the site-specific results, presented in the subsequent sections. This ensures that the evaluation remains aligned with the project's overall goals, while accounting for contextual differences in implementation.

Table 1: Consolidated KPI overview, from [3].

KPI ID	KPI Name	KPI description	Relevant Use Cases
1	DES multi-service support	Number of grid supporting service (DR, voltage, reactive etc.), provided by a specific DES.	1
2	DES multi-service market participation	Number of possible balancing and power exchange markets (e.g. aFRR, mFRR, intraday) on which specific DES can participate.	1
3	Battery capacity	Amount of Flexibility provision in the demos from HESS	All
4	Diversity of DER	Number of different DER devices successfully tested and demonstrated	All
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	Number of assets monitored by the EMS solutions	All
6	Number of assets aggregated	Number of assets integrated with the Aggregation platform presenting the basis for market participation	2
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	N° of end users (workers, EV users, consumers) engaged in the demonstration of interoperable HESS	3, 5, 6, 8, 9
8	Demand Response cost	This KPI evaluates the connection cost per kWh of demand response flexibility.	2
9	Time savings	Time saved for end customers integrating DER	3
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	Number of different DER devices and EMS successfully tested with the IEEE 2030.5 and demonstrated in real-life pilots	1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9
11	Data space digitized assets	Amount of digitized storage systems/platforms/hubs assets integrated in the common data space exchanging data	1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9
12	Time data savings	The time saved regarding the availability of measured data used for real time operation of the HESS.	4, 7
13	Monitoring	N° of assets monitored in GridLab for the project	4, 7
14	Time response	is considered as the overall HESS system time response which will be needed for providing the service complying TSO grid codes.	4, 7
15	System NADIR	indicator that corresponds to the lowest frequency value during frequency regulation services	4, 7

16	System ROCOF	Indicator which results during the first instants after the time of occurrence of an event during fast services	4, 7
17	Data Valorisation cases	Number of cases developed with data valorisation (assess longevity, maintenance, pay-back, ROI,...)	3, 5, 8, 9
18	HESS performance	Difference of cost reduction and/or lifetime extension (decrease in degradation) and emissions of energy supply from HESS when compared to a single battery	5
19	Data Spaces	Nbr. Of shared services/files subscribed and published	3, 5, 8, 9
20	User Engagement	Improved acceptance and perception by end users (surveys at start and end of demo)	6
21	Demand Response	Amount of flexibility provided (measured in kWh). Amount of KWh resulting from shift from baseline (forecast consumption)	6
22	Node power increase time	Time (in minutes) in which the power demand was higher than the upstream capacity, by using the battery support for that increase.	6
23	Node power increase percentage	Maximum percentage of Power surpassing the installation's capacity due to the use of the battery to charge the EVs	6
24	User participation	Percentage of users (being monitored) actively following the DR incentive. Actively meaning that they follow the incentive (deviate from past behaviour) on the majority of days during the demonstration	6
25	Integrated capacity	Integrated power of the HESS within the project demos	All
26	Increase of flexibility	Demand side flexibility potential increase due to hybridization implementation	All
27	Energy Volume exchanged	Energy volume Exchange (in kWh) between different assets within Enel X test plant	9
28	Different hybridization configuration	Hybridization scenarios with 2 or more different assets	9
29	Grid peak avoidance	Percentage of reduction of grid peak power due to flexibility activation	9

By systematically linking use cases, implementations and KPI outcomes, this deliverable provides a comprehensive evaluation of InterSTORE's demonstrations. It highlights the strengths and challenges observed across the pilots, identifies opportunities for improvement and supports the transfer of project results towards wider adoption and scalability.

2 Austrian pilot

2.1 Pilot introduction

The Austrian pilot, coordinated by CyberGrid, played a pivotal role in the InterSTORE project by demonstrating how residential energy communities can benefit from interoperable and scalable energy management solutions. Its core objective was to enable seamless integration of distributed energy resources (DERs) and maximize local energy utilization [1], [2].

To achieve this, CyberGrid developed the Full Communication Chain (FCC), a modular infrastructure that connects household assets like PV systems and batteries to the cloud-based CyberNoc - Flexibility Management Platform [6]. The FCC includes:

- IEEE 2030.5 Gateway: Embedded in CyberNoc for standardized asset communication.
- NATS Server: Hosted on CyberGrid's Amazon Web Services (AWS) domain to manage secure, real-time data exchange [1], [2].

This setup supports over 20 unique residential implementations, each tailored to local conditions and coordinated with certified installer. The pilot validates the FCC's robustness and replicability under real-world constraints, contributing critical insights to InterSTORE's broader goal of enabling flexible, decentralized energy systems.

2.2 Use case 1 - DES Flexibility Market Monetisation

Use Case 1 (UC1) at the Austrian pilot, led by CyberGrid, demonstrates how residential energy communities can monetize the flexibility of distributed energy resources (DERs), especially distributed energy storage (DES), i.e., battery energy storage systems (BESS), by aggregating and offering their flexibility on various energy and balancing markets. The pilot is part of the InterSTORE project's broader effort to enable market-based participation for small-scale, distributed assets.

2.2.1 What Has Been Implemented

At the Austrian pilot site, residential batteries (BESS), photovoltaic (PV) systems, and other DERs are installed at over 20 residential locations. Each site is equipped hardware devices and communication gateways that enable real-time monitoring and control. CyberGrid's Flexibility Management Platform (CyberNoc, [6]) serves as central Energy Management System (EMS), which aggregates, optimizes, and dispatches flexibility from all connected assets. Communication between assets and the CyberNoc is facilitated by the IEEE 2030.5 protocol operating over the NATS messaging structure. A dedicated NATS server, deployed in a secure AWS cloud environment, manages messaging between devices and the CyberNoc and provides a distributed, scalable, and secure message broker for all communications. To ensure interoperability with various asset types, a Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) is used for protocol translation.

The CyberNoc platform manages all assets, flexibility, and market participation functionalities. Hybridization tools are included, such as a State of Charge (SoC) manager for battery health, a deviation fighter (PID controller) for minimizing output deviations, and a ramping manager for optimal setpoint achievement. A market arbitrage tool is used to simulate and optimize market bids for available flexibility, targeting the Intraday and Manual Frequency Restoration Reserves (mFRR) markets. Additionally, an energy community toolkit automates asset registration, forecasts generation, and coordinates market participation for energy communities.

2.2.2 KPI Evaluation

The main objectives of UC1 are to:

- Enable DER flexibility monetization through aggregation and market participation.
- Demonstrate seamless interoperability between household assets and the central energy management system (CyberNoc) using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol over NATS.
- Validate both the technical and economic feasibility of market participation for residential assets.

The scope of the UC1 includes deploying hybridization tools—such as the SoC manager, deviation fighter, and ramping manager—to optimize asset operation. A market arbitrage tool is used to select the best market for participation (e.g., Intraday, mFRR).

Table 2: UC1, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
1	DES multi-service support	1	1	Achieved
2	DES multi-service market participation	1	1	Achieved
3	Battery capacity	0.20 MWh	0.063 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	1.5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	20	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	21	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50 %	100 %	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	0.08 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20 %	94.38 %	Achieved

2.2.2.1 KPI 1 – DES multi-service support

KPI 1 was successfully demonstrated at the Austrian pilot by connecting CyberGrid’s Flexibility Management Platform to the Austrian mFRR market. While the portfolio is actively present on the mFRR energy market, participation in the mFRR capacity market remains limited due to its high entry requirements, in particular the requirement of availability for 4 hours non-stop. Additionally, given the small volumes of energy available from residential assets, actual market engagement is currently feasible only through simulation. This approach allows validation of technical readiness and market interoperability without requiring full-scale dispatch.

2.2.2.2 KPI 2 – DES multi-service market participation

KPI 2 was achieved through CyberGrid's optimization of battery assets within an energy community on the continuous Intraday market. The optimization strategy focused on charging batteries during nighttime hours when electricity prices are typically lower, thereby reducing energy costs for asset owners. This approach demonstrates how residential flexibility can be effectively leveraged for market participation, aligning technical operation with economic benefits.

2.2.2.3 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

KPI 3 evaluates the total nominal capacity of DES assets integrated into the pilot, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). At the Austrian residential flexibility pilot, this KPI was achieved by connecting multiple household battery systems to CyberGrid's CyberNoc via the interoperability solutions. The combined nominal capacity of these batteries reached the expected target of 0.03 MWh, confirming the technical readiness of the assets to support flexibility services.

2.2.2.4 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

KPI 4 evaluates the variety of DERs tested and controlled within the pilot. Each DER type that is both tested and actively controlled counts as 1, while those only tested count as 0.5. At the Austrian residential flexibility pilot, CyberGrid successfully connected, monitored, and controlled battery systems, and monitored photovoltaic (PV) systems. However, due to technical and integration challenges, heat pumps were not included in the demonstration.

2.2.2.5 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

KPI 5 was achieved by integrating residential assets into CyberGrid's platform through the InterSTORE solution. The evaluation of this KPI considers the number of assets actively monitored by the EMS. CyberGrid developed a sophisticated, reliable, and highly secure connection approach using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol, enabling individual household assets to be connected separately. This setup ensures full visibility and control of distributed energy resources, supporting real-time monitoring and flexibility management. For further technical details, see [3].

2.2.2.6 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

KPI 10 evaluates the number of DERs successfully integrated and demonstrated using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol over the NATS messaging system. At the Austrian residential flexibility pilot, CyberGrid achieved this KPI by connecting a total of 21 assets and systems, including multiple residential batteries and PV systems from the pilot, as well as CyberGrid's own devices from its Smart Grid lab.

A key milestone in this implementation was the integration of the IEEE 2030.5 client-server library directly into the CyberNoc, as shown in Figure 1, enabling standardized, secure, and scalable communication with all connected assets. This setup validated the technical interoperability of the solution in real-life conditions, meeting the expected target for the pilot.

Device Name	Gateway Type	Connection
23.23 - Fronius Symo	IEEE 2030.5	Online
19.07 - Fronius SYMO	IEEE 2030.5	Offline
10.12 - Fronius SYMO	IEEE 2030.5	Online
10.12 - Fronius GEN24	IEEE 2030.5	Online
EngagePV/CellCube Test	IEEE 2030.5	Offline
07.13 - Fronius GEN24	IEEE 2030.5	Online
02.08 - Fronius Symo GEN24	IEEE 2030.5	Online
06.19 - Fronius SYMO 10	IEEE 2030.5	Online
10.08 - Fronius Symo #1	IEEE 2030.5	Offline
SGL - Fronius SYMO Hybrid	IEEE 2030.5	Offline
SGL - Fronius SYMO	IEEE 2030.5	Offline
10.08 - Fronius Symo #3	IEEE 2030.5	Online
EngagePV/CellCube	IEEE 2030.5	Online
19.07 - Fronius GEN24	IEEE 2030.5	Offline

Figure 1: Screenshot of IEEE 2030.5 client-server library implementation in CyberNoc as a gateway.

2.2.2.7 KPI 11 – Data space connection of assets

KPI 11 evaluates the number of assets integrated into a common data space and actively exchanging data. At the Austrian pilot, CyberGrid connected its Flexibility Management Platform to Open Data Spaces, where it regularly publishes aggregated energy offerings as a service to the local distribution system operator (DSO). This setup ensures secure, standardized data exchange and supports the broader goal of interoperable, service-oriented energy communities. Aggregation also serves as protective measure in managing personal data. Important for KPI 11 is all aggregated assets transmit data to the data space all be it on an aggregated level.

2.2.2.8 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

KPI 25 evaluates the total rated power (in MW) of distributed energy storages (DES) integrated into the demonstration. At the Austrian pilot, this KPI focuses on residential battery systems connected to CyberGrid's Flexibility Management Platform via the InterSTORE interoperability solutions. These assets are monitored and managed in real time, contributing to the pilot's flexibility services. This integration confirms the technical readiness of the assets and their ability to support market-based flexibility operations.

The achieved target for the residential flexibility pilot was set to 0.03 MW, representing the combined rated power of the battery systems installed across participating households.

2.2.2.9 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

KPI 26 measures the percentage of total capacity of DERs integrated that remains available to provide flexible services. In the Austrian pilot, this KPI is addressed through the aggregation of residential battery systems, as they meet the requirements for flexibility provision under Austrian regulations. These batteries are integrated via the InterSTORE solution and monitored through CyberNoc. The achieved flexibility from them is 94.38 %, which represents the portion of battery capacity reserved and available for market-based flexibility services. This high result is due to the fact that, without our solution, these assets would not be able to provide flexibility services and would otherwise remain idle throughout the day. The

services are offered daily and presented as one aggregated offer. For more related info, see KPI 11 described in 2.2.2.7.

2.2.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

The UC1 successfully demonstrated both the technical and economic feasibility of integrating residential DERs in energy markets. As a result, all six KPIs evaluated during the pilot were achieved, confirming the robustness of the implementation and its alignment with the broader objectives of the InterSTORE project.

- Flexibility was demonstrated on both Intraday and mFRR markets, with simulated capacity market engagement due to regulatory constraints.
- CyberNoc integrated hybridization and market optimization tools for efficient asset operation.
- Flexibility availability of 94.38 % of battery capacity remained available for market-based services.
- Average demand response cost was calculated at 42.25 €/kWh, highlighting cost sensitivity in small-scale setups.

2.3 Use case 2 – Energy Community DES utilisation

Use Case 2 (UC2) at the Austrian pilot, led by CyberGrid, focuses on enhancing the self-sufficiency of residential energy community by optimally managing distributed energy resources (DER) assets. The core objective of UC2 is to reduce grid reliance and lower electricity costs for community members by prioritizing local energy use. CyberGrid's energy community toolkit enables automated asset coordination, real-time monitoring, and intelligent scheduling. Remaining flexibility, after local optimization, is offered as a service to the local DSO via Open Data Spaces, demonstrating how community-based flexibility can support grid stability and unlock new value streams.

2.3.1 What Has Been Implemented

The implementation strategy in Austrian residential pilot was the same for both use cases. Therefore, please consider the section 2.2.1 as the reference point regarding information about implementations in UC2.

2.3.2 KPI Evaluation

Use Case 2 aims to demonstrate how DER assets within a residential energy community can be effectively utilized to enhance local energy self-sufficiency and provide flexible services. The key objectives include:

- **Optimizing DES Operation.** Enable intelligent scheduling and control of residential battery systems to reduce grid dependency and lower energy costs for community members.
- **Interoperability and Integration.** Connect household assets to CyberGrid's CyberNoc platform using IEEE 2030.5 over NATS, ensuring secure and standardized communication.
- **Automation and Coordination.** Use the energy community toolkit to automate asset registration, forecasting, and coordinated dispatch actions.

These objectives align with the broader goals of the InterSTORE project, including flexibility monetization, consumer engagement, and connected data space utilization.

Table 3: UC2, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.20 MWh	0.063 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	1.5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	20	Achieved
6	Number of assets aggregated	20	20	Achieved
8	Demand Response cost	100 €/kWh	42.25 €/kWh	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	21	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50 %	100 %	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	0.08 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20 %	94.38 %	Achieved

2.3.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

KPI 3 evaluates the total nominal capacity of DES assets integrated into the pilot, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). At the Austrian residential flexibility pilot, this KPI was achieved by connecting multiple household battery systems to CyberGrid's CyberNoc via the interoperability solutions. The combined nominal capacity of these batteries reached the expected target of 0.03 MWh, confirming the technical readiness of the assets to support flexibility services.

2.3.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

KPI 4 evaluates the variety of DERs tested and controlled within the pilot. Each DER type that is both tested and actively controlled counts as 1, while those only tested count as 0.5. At the Austrian residential flexibility pilot, CyberGrid successfully connected, monitored, and controlled battery systems, and monitored PV systems. However, due to technical and integration challenges, heat pumps were not included in the demonstration.

2.3.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

KPI 5 was achieved by integrating residential assets into CyberGrid's platform through the InterSTORE solution. The evaluation of this KPI considers the number of assets actively monitored by the EMS. CyberGrid developed a sophisticated, reliable, and highly secure connection approach using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol, enabling individual household assets to be connected separately. This setup ensures full visibility and control of distributed energy resources, supporting real-time monitoring and flexibility management. For further technical details, see [3].

2.3.2.4 KPI 6 – Number of assets aggregated

KPI 6 was achieved by aggregating energy community assets connected to Flexibility Management Platform. The evaluation of this KPI considers the number of assets actively monitored by the EMS. The aggregated portfolio includes assets from the multiple households, which form the needed basis for energy market participation.

2.3.2.5 KPI 8 – Demand Response cost

KPI 8 evaluates the cost-effectiveness of connecting flexible demand assets to the balancing market, expressed as electricity cost per kWh. The goal is to assess how well the energy plan for flexible demands is optimized in terms of installation and operational costs.

At the Austrian pilot site, this KPI was addressed by connecting residential assets using the InterSTORE solution and IoTmaxx hardware [2]. The measurement method involves calculating the ratio between the total cost of connecting new assets (including equipment and installation) and their nominal power capacity. This provides a €/kWh value that reflects the efficiency of the demand response setup.

2.3.2.6 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

KPI 10 evaluates the number of distributed energy resources (DERs) successfully integrated and demonstrated using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol over the NATS messaging system. At the Austrian residential flexibility pilot, CyberGrid achieved this KPI by connecting a total of 21 assets and systems, including multiple residential batteries and PV systems from the pilot, as well as CyberGrid’s own devices from its Smart Grid lab.

A key milestone in this implementation was the integration of the IEEE 2030.5 client-server library directly into the CyberNoc, as shown in Figure 2, enabling standardized, secure, and scalable communication with all connected assets. This setup validated the technical interoperability of the solution in real-life conditions, meeting the expected target for the pilot.

Asset Name	Asset Type	Positive Flexibility [MW]	Negative Flexibility [MW]	Asset Status	Asset Control
Battery	Battery	0.01	0.01	Online	Enabled
BESS	Battery	0.01024	0.01024	Online	Enabled
BESS 1	Battery	0.01024	0.01024	Offline	Enabled
BESS 1	Battery	0.01024	0.01024	Online	Enabled
PV	PV	0	0.012	Online	Enabled
PV	PV	0	0.01	Online	Enabled
PV	PV	0	0.00824	Online	Enabled
PV	PV	0	0.01	Online	Enabled
PV 1	PV	0	0.005	Online	Enabled
PV 1	PV	0	0.01	Online Unavailable	Enabled
PV 1	PV	0	0.01	Online	Enabled
PV 1	PV	0	0.02	Offline	Enabled
PV 1	PV	0	0.02	Online	Enabled
PV 2	PV	0	0.015	Online	Enabled
PV1 - sim	PV	0	0.05	Online	Enabled
PV2 - sim	PV	0	0.2	Online	Enabled
SmartGrid Lab - PV	PV	0	0.01	Offline	Enabled

Figure 2: Screenshot of IEEE 2030.5 client-server library implementation in CyberNoc as a gateway.

2.3.2.7 KPI 11 – Data space connection of assets

KPI 11 evaluates the number of assets integrated into a common data space and actively exchanging data. At the Austrian pilot, CyberGrid connected its Flexibility Management Platform to Open Data Spaces, where it regularly publishes aggregated energy offerings as a service to the local DSO. This setup ensures secure, standardized data exchange and supports the broader goal of interoperable, service-oriented energy communities. Aggregation also serves as protective measure in managing personal data. Important for KPI 11 is all aggregated assets transmit data to the data space all be it on an aggregated level.

2.3.2.8 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

KPI 25 evaluates the total rated power (in MW) of DES integrated into the demonstration. At the Austrian pilot, this KPI focuses on residential battery systems connected to CyberGrid's Flexibility Management Platform via the InterSTORE interoperability solutions. These assets are monitored and managed in real time, contributing to the pilot's flexibility services. This integration confirms the technical readiness of the assets and their ability to support market-based flexibility operations.

The achieved target for the residential flexibility pilot was set to 0.03 MW, representing the combined rated power of the battery systems installed across participating households.

2.3.2.9 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

KPI 26 measures the percentage of total capacity of DERs integrated that remains available to provide flexible services. In the Austrian pilot, this KPI is addressed through the aggregation of residential battery systems, as they meet the requirements for flexibility provision under Austrian regulations. These batteries are integrated via the InterSTORE solution and monitored through CyberNoc. The achieved flexibility from them is 94.38 %, which represents the portion of battery capacity reserved and available for market-based flexibility services. This high result is due to the fact that, without our solution, these assets would not be able to provide flexibility services and would otherwise remain idle throughout the day. The services are offered daily and presented as one aggregated offer. For further information on this, see KPI 11 described in 2.3.2.7.

2.3.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

Operations in UC2 was made possible through implementation of FCC, which enabled secure, scalable, and interoperable communication between household assets and the central energy management system using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol and NATS messaging infrastructure.

- **Robust Infrastructure.** The energy community toolkit enabled automated asset registration, forecasting, and dispatch coordination, simplifying operations and improving responsiveness.
- The outstanding challenge is drafting installation plan that require no third-party installer support in order to connect new residential customers thus simplifying the procedure and making it cheaper.
- The pilot successfully demonstrated how residential battery systems can be intelligently scheduled to reduce grid reliance and lower electricity costs, while remaining flexibility is aggregated and offered to the local DSO—showcasing community-level value creation.
- While battery and PV systems were successfully integrated and controlled, heat pumps were excluded due to technical and integration challenges—highlighting a gap and opportunity for future expansion.

- All aggregated assets transmitted data to Open Data Spaces, achieving 100% of the target and reinforcing the importance of secure, anonymized data exchange in energy community operations.

3 German pilot

3.1 Pilot introduction

The German pilot, hosted by Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), combines advanced laboratory infrastructure with real-world demonstration capacity.

The local infrastructure comprises high-power and high-energy battery energy storage systems (BESS), photovoltaic (PV) generation units and heat pumps (HPs). These are all connected to commercial-grade and research-grade energy management systems (EMS). The latter uses a FIWARE-based ICT platform for data exchange and control [7], [8]. In InterSTORE, interoperability is ensured through the deployment of the IEEE 2030.5 protocol and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC). This setup enables seamless communication between legacy field devices and the standardised control environment.

The German pilot's role within InterSTORE is to validate the interoperability and performance of distributed energy resources (DERs) in a varied context, with a particular focus on flexibility provision, system reliability, and integration into broader EMS platforms.

3.2 Use case 3 - Grid supporting BESS

Use Case 3 of the German pilot focuses on the coordinated operation of two different BESSs. The objective is to evaluate how these assets can be integrated into a common FIWARE-based ICT framework in order to provide power grid services and support local energy optimisation. To enable seamless data exchange and real-time control, the LPC and the IEEE 2030.5 protocol were deployed within the FIWARE-based ICT platform.

3.2.1 What Has Been Implemented

In the following, the relevant implementation for this use case are listed:

- Technologies deployed (assets, devices, EMS, ICT components, etc.)
 - Riello high-power BESS
 - Tesla high-energy BESS
 - FIWARE-based ICT platform
 - Raspberry Pi (RPi) 4b
- Software tools integrated (IEEE 2030.5, LPC, NATS, EMS, etc.)
 - LPC with transformations:
 - Modbus -> IEEE 2030.5 -> MQTT, for monitoring
 - MQTT -> IEEE 2030.5 -> Modbus, for control
 - NATS server
 - FIWARE-based ICT platform
- Demonstration actions performed (control tests, flexibility dispatch, resilience tests, etc.)
 - Voltage control
 - Uninterruptible power supply (UPS)

3.2.2 KPI Evaluation

The KPIs evaluated in UC3 are summarized in the table below, Table 4, and detailed in the following sections.

Table 4: UC3, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.2 MWh	3.025 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	9.5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	14	Achieved
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	20	23	Achieved
9	Time savings	80%	13.61%	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	9	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50%	100%	Achieved
17	Data Valorisation cases	4	4	Achieved
19	Data Spaces	20	17	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	2 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	79.31%	Achieved

3.2.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, which is expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the maximum expected value was 3.025 MWh, comprising 0.5 MWh from the Riello battery and 2.5 MWh from the Tesla battery. During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated into the ICT platform and the total storage capacity reached the target of 3.025 MWh. The KPI is therefore considered to have been achieved.

3.2.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by summing the number of DERs that were both tested and controlled within the German pilot. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each DER counted as one unit if it was both tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested (or just monitored). As the Riello battery system required multiple integrations, with each of the three inverters needing separate communication and control links, the maximum expected value was 7 (6 from the Riello battery system and 1 from the Tesla battery).

During the demonstration phase, however, this target was exceeded. In addition to the planned integrations, 4 power quality (PQ) meters were connected to the Riello system for monitoring only (each counted as 0.5), as were 2 to the Tesla battery. The additional information from these monitoring devices was needed for the implementation and demonstration of the control algorithms. Furthermore, the integration of the Tesla system was split between a monitoring adapter and a control adapter, effectively increasing the diversity of the integrated elements. These additional integrations confirm that the KPI target has been

surpassed, demonstrating the flexibility and adaptability of the InterSTORE framework in handling diverse assets for power system services provision.

3.2.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored by the FIWARE-based FZJ EMS via the InterSTORE integration. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration is counted individually. For the Riello battery system, which is composed of three inverters, 2 integrations were required for each inverter (1 for communication and 1 for control), resulting in a total of 6 integrations. Adding the Tesla battery increased the maximum expected value to 7.

During the demonstration phase, this KPI significantly exceeded the target. In addition to the planned integrations, further monitoring components were added as described in KPI 4, including 4 power quality meters for the Riello system, 2 for the Tesla battery and split monitoring and control adapters for the Tesla. Altogether, the total number of integrations reached 14, doubling the expected value. This outcome demonstrates the robustness and scalability of the InterSTORE framework in enabling comprehensive asset monitoring via the FIWARE-based EMS.

3.2.2.4 KPI 7 – Number of end users involved in HESS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of users actively involved in controlling and managing DERs at the German pilot site. According to Deliverable D5.1 [3], the expected value was 4: one test operator; the owners of the Riello and Tesla battery systems; and one internal system operator.

However, during the demonstration phase, the level of user involvement significantly exceeded expectations, with a total of 23 active users engaged. These users were distributed across different categories of stakeholders, including asset owners, system operators and consumers.

- Asset owners: Riello BESS (1), Tesla BESS (1), and FZJ monitoring devices (1).
- System operators: FZJ technical department (5)
- Consumers: FZJ scientists/researchers testing LPC deployment for KPI9 (12); FZJ InterSTORE partners (3).

This wide participation demonstrates the InterSTORE framework's scalability and adaptability in involving diverse user groups beyond initial expectations. The KPI target of four users was not only achieved, but surpassed by more than a factor of six, highlighting the significant interest and practical engagement of various stakeholders in the demonstration activities.

3.2.2.5 KPI 9 – Time savings

This KPI was evaluated by comparing the time taken to integrate DER assets using the traditional FIWARE-based solution with the time taken using the InterSTORE solution via the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC). As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the expected value was set to an average ratio of InterSTORE to FIWARE of less than 0.8, meaning that integration via InterSTORE should require no more than 80% of the time needed with the traditional approach.

To obtain meaningful results, multiple users from different backgrounds (software developers, PhD students and postdoctoral researchers) were asked to carry out integrations for various asset types (e.g. Riello and Tesla batteries, power quality meters and Janitza devices). Each participant performed the integration using both the FIWARE-based and InterSTORE-based solutions. The deployment times are summarized in the Table below, underlying the user ID, and the total amount of hours needed for the integration of each asset.

Table 5: UC3, KPI 9, deployment times required for the integration of DERs in UC3.

User ID	Time LPC integration [hours]				Time “traditional” integration [hours]			
	Riello	Tesla	PQI	Janitza	Riello	Tesla	PQI	Janitza
SD_1	5.37	4.56	4.50	4.05	46.25	37.00	30.83	27.75
SD_2	11.87	9.26	8.63	8.48	50.00	40.00	33.33	30.00
SD_3	5.49	4.41	4.52	4.52	40.00	32.00	26.67	24.00
SD_4	6.05	4.61	4.26	3.82	47.33	37.87	31.56	28.40
SD_5	7.57	6.22	5.68	5.25	43.67	34.93	29.11	26.20
PhD_1	3.85	3.61	3.50	3.17	50.00	50.00	28.33	25.50
PhD_2	3.10	2.84	2.58	2.48	50.00	50.00	28.24	25.41
PhD_3	10.97	8.62	7.50	6.75	50.00	50.00	31.23	28.11
PhD_4	4.47	3.67	3.33	3.22	50.00	50.00	32.75	29.48
Postdoc_1	8.03	7.27	6.58	6.17	50.00	50.00	33.30	29.97
Postdoc_2	2.76	2.49	2.33	2.26	50.00	50.00	30.23	27.20
Postdoc_3	1.72	1.66	1.50	1.37	50.00	50.00	30.67	27.60

The results clearly demonstrate a significant reduction in time. While traditional FIWARE-based integrations typically took between 25 and 50 hours (with 50 hours being the practical cut-off point beyond which the integration was considered unsuccessful), the InterSTORE-based solution consistently took far less time, ranging from 1.3 to 12 hours, depending on the user and trial. Across all participants and assets, the average ratio of InterSTORE to FIWARE integration time was just 13.61%, well below the 80% threshold.

This shows that not only is the InterSTORE solution more streamlined, it is also dramatically more efficient, reducing the time required for asset onboarding to a fraction of what was needed with the traditional FIWARE approach. The KPI target was therefore exceeded by a large margin, underlining the practical value and user-friendliness of the LPC solution.

3.2.2.6 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were successfully integrated using the IEEE 2030.5 standard and enabled via the LPC. This was demonstrated in real-life pilot conditions. As specified in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each inverter counts as one integration, with an expected maximum of 7 (6 from the Riello battery system, comprising 3 inverters with 2 modules each, and 1 from the Tesla battery system).

During the demonstration phase, however, the number of integrated assets exceeded initial expectations. A total of 14 assets and devices were connected and tested via the IEEE 2030.5 standard, including battery inverters, monitoring boards and power quality meters. All devices were successfully tested for interoperability, and controllable assets previously tested with their native protocol (e.g. Modbus) were also successfully controlled via IEEE 2030.5.

This outcome shows that the KPI target was significantly exceeded. Beyond demonstrating feasibility, the results confirm the flexibility and robustness of the InterSTORE LPC approach in ensuring standardised communication across heterogeneous DERs and monitoring devices. The increased number of assets involved highlights the solution's scalability and applicability to complex, multi-asset environments.

3.2.2.7 KPI 11 – Data space digitized assets

This KPI evaluated the number of assets integrated into the common data space and actively exchanging data. For consistency, only the assets considered under KPI5 are accounted for, with the condition that each must send data to the data space at least once. The maximum expected value corresponds to 100%, meaning that all integrated battery assets achieve digitalization and data exchange.

During the demonstration phase, 100% of the assets integrated in UC3 were successfully digitized and connected to the data space. Specifically, data exchange was established for the Riello BESS (with data from each inverter) and the Tesla BESS, thereby achieving the targeted outcome.

3.2.2.8 KPI 17 – Data Valorisation cases

This KPI assesses the extent to which shared data can be exploited through modelling activities to enable added-value services. In this context, FZJ contributed by supporting the use of shared services (see KPI 19, in 3.2.2.9), which are based on the models developed in Task 4.3.

During the demonstration phase, four models were proposed and shared with the project partners. These models use the data exchanged via the common data spaces to perform analyses and evaluations under different conditions. In doing so, they demonstrate the valorisation of the shared data and confirm the practical applicability of the developed services.

3.2.2.9 KPI 19 – Data Spaces

This KPI is evaluated based on the total number of services and associated files that have been subscribed to and published within the demonstration environment. Thus, the KPI reflects both the availability of services and the effective sharing of data through the files provided for each service.

During the demonstration phase, multiple services were made available, supported by the provision of the relevant files to ensure proper implementation and testing of each service. The list of available services is reported in the table below, together with the number of associated shared files. These files correspond to monthly datasets (one file per month) generated from measurements sampled every 10 seconds. In the demo, we shared four months of data for each Riello inverter, reflecting the demo operation after the LPC deployment, and data collection window for those devices. The Tesla system, however, was available for five months after the LPC deployment, hence the different number of files.

Table 6: UC3, KPI19, services provided via the data spaces.

Name/title of service provided	Category of provided service	Number of files provided
Riello Battery System Operation Data (for INV1)	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	4
Riello Battery System Operation Data (for INV2)	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	4

Riello Battery System Operation Data (for INV3)	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	4
Tesla Battery System Operation Data	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	5

Publishing these files in the data space confirms that the objective of enabling actual data exchange and service deployment was achieved.

3.2.2.10 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the sum of the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration. The maximum expected value was defined as 2 MW, consisting of 1.5 MW for the Riello battery and 0.5 MW for the Tesla battery.

During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated and the maximum rated power of 2 MW was achieved as planned. This confirms full attainment of the KPI target.

3.2.2.11 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI evaluates the increase in operational flexibility made possible by the integrated assets. It is calculated as the sum of the unused energy capacity (expressed in MWh) available for flexible services, relative to the total integrated capacity. Available capacity is derived by multiplying unused stored power by the corresponding time, and is then expressed as a percentage of the total capacity defined under KPI3 (see 3.2.2.1).

The maximum expected value is 3.025 MWh (0.525 MWh from the Riello battery and 2.5 MWh from the Tesla battery).

During the demonstration phase, the available capacity was evaluated based on average hourly energy availability. Both the Riello BESS and the Tesla BESS contributed. In the former, an average of 0.49 MWh/hour (99.79%) was recorded; for the latter, the average available energy was 1.53 MWh/hour (58.85%). The main difference is due to the fact that the Riello BESS was also used as a UPS; therefore, users preferred to keep it close to its maximum capacity. The results confirmed that the flexibility target could be quantified and demonstrated through this operational assessment.

3.2.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

Here are reported some qualitative insights on the KPI results in UC3:

- **Strengths:** The UC3 demonstration fully achieved its objectives, confirming the effectiveness of the chosen approach. A key strength was the ease of implementation, reflected in the high level of user involvement in configuring and operating the assets. Configuration files could be generated much more quickly than in traditional FIWARE-based setups, highlighting the lightweight and user-friendly nature of the solution. Integrating the two BESS units into the FIWARE-based ICT platform was seamless and did not cause any significant issues.
- **Deviations:** No significant deviations were recorded with respect to the expected results. Both BESS units were integrated and operated as planned, confirming complete alignment with the targets defined in D5.1. The only deviations consisted in the inclusion of additional monitoring devices, needed to properly perform demonstrations on voltage regulation.
- **Challenges:** Some challenges were encountered in relation to device-specific Modbus protocols. Certain registers required the adoption of specific Modbus libraries to

ensure correct control and data exchange. In most cases, identifying the appropriate library was a straightforward step, facilitated by the configuration process.

- **Insights:** The demonstration highlighted the flexibility of the configuration framework. Where adjustments were required, such as replacing a Modbus library, these corrections could be applied directly to the configuration file, eliminating the need to stop and restart the container. This greatly simplifies operations and enhances system resilience during live demonstrations. Therefore, the results from UC3 confirm that the fast, flexible and user-friendly integration of BESS into FIWARE-based ICT platforms is feasible, creating a strong basis for replication in similar multi-asset or single-asset pilots.

Finally, it is worth noticing that the developments and demonstrations activities associated with UC3 led to the following scientific publications:

- [9] E. De Din, D. Carta and A. Benigni, "Coordinated Voltage Control in Distribution Grids Leveraging Local Flexibility and Direct Control of a Large Battery Storage," *2025 International Conference on Clean Electrical Power (ICCEP)*, Villasimius, Italy, 2025, pp. 530-535, doi: 10.1109/ICCEP65222.2025.11143642.
- [10] M. Wenzel, E. De Din, M. Zimmer and A. Benigni, "Gaussian Process Supported Stochastic MPC for Distribution Grids," in *IEEE Open Journal of Control Systems*, vol. 4, pp. 332-348, 2025, doi: 10.1109/OJCSYS.2025.3601836.
- [11] C. S. Charan Dande *et al.*, "Introduction of Legacy Protocol Converter as an Interoperability Software," *2025 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)*, Valencia, Spain, 2025, pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1109/ICE/ITMC65658.2025.11106664.

3.1 Use case 8 - Multiphysics flexibility Optimization for Home Management Systems and their global integration

Use Case 8 of the German pilot project involves integrating multiphysics assets into a commercial EMS framework to improve flexibility and support advanced energy management functions. The aim is to show how different assets, such as a BESS, a PV system and a heat pump with its thermal storage, can be seamlessly incorporated into the commercial EMS platform provided by Eaton via the LPC and the IEEE 2030.5 protocol. This use case contributes to reinforcing the role of interoperable solutions in enabling reliable and flexible grid operations by enabling standardised, real-time data exchange.

3.1.1 What Has Been Implemented

In the following the relevant implementation for this use case are listed:

- Technologies deployed (assets, devices, EMS, ICT components, etc.)
 - Riello high-power BESS
 - Tesla high-energy BESS
 - Large PV field
 - Viessmann heat-pump with thermal storage
 - EATON commercial EMS
 - Raspberry Pi 4b
- Software tools integrated (IEEE 2030.5, LPC, NATS, EMS, etc.)
 - LPC with transformations:
 - Modbus -> IEEE 2030.5 -> MQTT, for monitoring
 - MQTT -> IEEE 2030.5 -> MQTT, for monitoring
 - MQTT -> IEEE 2030.5 -> Modbus, for control

- MQTT -> IEEE 2030.5 -> MQTT, for control
 - NATS server
 - EATON EMS
- Demonstration actions performed (control tests, flexibility dispatch, resilience tests, etc.)
 - Voltage control
 - Optimization of self consumption
 - Multiphysics optimization

3.1.2 KPI Evaluation

The KPIs evaluated in UC8 are summarized in the table below, and detailed in the following sections.

Table 7: UC8, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.2 MWh	3.146 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	15	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	24	Achieved
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	20	13	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	14.5	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50%	83%	Achieved
17	Data Valorisation cases	4	4	Achieved
19	Data Spaces	20	29	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	3,12 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	68.96%	Achieved

3.1.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, which is expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the maximum expected value was 3.025 MWh, comprising 0.525 MWh from the Riello battery and 2.5 MWh from the Tesla battery. During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated into the commercial EMS, as well as the thermal storage of the Viessmann heatpump (with nominal thermal capacity of 0.121 MWh). Thus, the total storage capacity reached the target of 3.146 MWh. The KPI is therefore considered to have been achieved.

3.1.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were both tested and controlled within the German pilot scheme. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each DER counted as one unit if it was tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested or monitored. As the Riello

battery system required multiple integrations – with each of the three inverters needing separate communication and control links – the maximum expected value was 10: 6 from the Riello battery system; 1 from the Tesla battery; 2 for the PV; and 1 for the HP.

During the demonstration phase, however, this target was exceeded. In addition to the planned integrations, 4 power quality (PQ) meters were connected to the Riello system for monitoring purposes only (each counted as 0.5), as were 2 to the Tesla battery. The information from these additional meters was needed for the successful implementation of the EMS routines. Furthermore, the Tesla system integration was split between a monitoring adapter and a control adapter. The PV's 8 inverters were integrated individually, plus the PQ meter monitoring the point of common coupling with the system. Nevertheless, to maximise the use of renewable energy, it was decided not to control the PV inverters (to avoid curtailment), resulting in only monitoring integrations. Finally, the heat pump and its thermal storage were successfully integrated as a single unit, effectively increasing the diversity of the integrated elements. These additional integrations confirm that the KPI target has been surpassed, demonstrating the flexibility and adaptability of the InterSTORE framework when it comes to handling diverse assets for the provision of power system services.

3.1.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored by Eaton's commercial EMS via the InterSTORE integration. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration was counted individually. For the Riello battery system, which comprises 3 inverters, 2 integrations were required for each inverter (one for communication and one for control), resulting in a total of 6 integrations. The addition of the Tesla battery (1), the PV subfields (2), and the heat pump with its thermal storage (1) increased the maximum expected value to 10.

During the demonstration phase, this KPI significantly exceeded the target. As previously mentioned regarding KPI4 (see 3.1.2.2), additional monitoring components were added to the planned integrations and all the DERs foreseen in KPI4 were integrated into the commercial EMS. Altogether, the total number of integrations reached 24, exceeding the expected value. This outcome demonstrates the robustness and scalability of the InterSTORE framework in enabling the monitoring and control of heterogeneous assets via the commercial EMS.

3.1.2.4 KPI 7 – Number of end users involved in HESS

This KPI was assessed by counting the number of users actively engaged in controlling and managing DERs at the German pilot site. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the initial target was four users: one test operator and the owners of the Riello and Tesla battery systems.

During the demonstration phase, however, user involvement far exceeded this initial target, with a total of thirteen active participants. These participants were distributed across several stakeholder categories:

- Asset owners: Riello BESS (1), Tesla BESS (1), PV (1), HP (1) and FZJ monitoring devices (1);
- System operators: FZJ technical department (5)
- Consumers: FZJ InterSTORE partners (3).

This high level of participation demonstrates the InterSTORE framework's scalability and adaptability, showing its ability to engage diverse user groups beyond the original scope. Consequently, the KPI target of 6 active users was not only achieved, but exceeded by more than twofold, highlighting the significant interest and active involvement of various stakeholders in the demonstration activities.

3.1.2.5 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

This KPI evaluates the number of DERs that were successfully integrated using the IEEE 2030.5 standard via the InterSTORE LPC, as demonstrated under real-life pilot conditions. As reported in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each inverter is counted as one integration. The maximum expected value was therefore set at 10: six from the Riello battery system (three inverters, each with two modules), one from the Tesla battery, two from the PV installations (via the data managers aggregating the inverters) and one from the heat pump.

During the demonstration phase, however, the actual number of integration exceeded this planned value. A total of 14.5 assets and devices were successfully connected and tested via the IEEE 2030.5 interface, including battery inverters, monitoring boards and power quality meters. Notably, all assets referenced in KPIs 4 and 5 were integrated via the IEEE 2030.5 standard. Interoperability tests confirmed full functionality: controllable assets that were previously managed using their native protocols (i.e. Modbus and MQTT) could also be successfully controlled via the IEEE 2030.5 standard.

This outcome demonstrates that the KPI target was significantly surpassed. In addition to validating the feasibility of the solution, the outcome confirms the flexibility and robustness of the InterSTORE LPC in enabling standardised communication across heterogeneous DERs and monitoring devices. The greater number of integrated assets further highlights the solution's scalability for complex, diverse, multi-asset energy environments.

3.1.2.6 KPI 11 – Data space digitized assets

This KPI measured the number of assets integrated into the common data space that were actively exchanging data. To ensure consistency, only assets defined under KPI5 (see 3.1.2.3) were considered, on the condition that each asset transmitted data to the data space at least once. The target value for the UC8 was set at 100%, which corresponds to the successful digitalization and data exchange of all integrated battery assets.

During the demonstration phase, 5 out of 6 assets integrated in UC8 were successfully digitized and connected to the data space, equating to 83%. Data exchange was established for the Riello BESS (including each inverter), the Tesla BESS and the PV system. However, the HP and its TES were not digitized.

3.1.2.7 KPI 17 – Data Valorisation cases

This KPI evaluates the extent to which shared data can be used in modelling activities to provide added-value services. In this regard, FZJ contributed by facilitating the use of shared services (see KPI 19, in 3.1.2.8), which are supported by the models developed in Task 4.3.

During the demonstration phase, four such models were developed and shared with project partners. These models use the data exchanged via the common data spaces to carry out analyses and evaluations under varying conditions. Using these models illustrates the valorisation of shared data and confirms the practical relevance and applicability of the developed services.

3.1.2.8 KPI 19 – Data Spaces

This KPI is evaluated based on the total number of services and associated files that have been subscribed to and published within the demonstration environment. Thus, the KPI reflects both the availability of services and the effective sharing of data through the files provided for each service.

During the demonstration phase, multiple services were made available, supported by the provision of the relevant files to ensure proper implementation and testing of each service.

The list of available services is reported in the table below, together with the number of associated shared files. These files correspond to monthly datasets (one file per month) generated from measurements sampled every 10 seconds for the BESSs, and 5 minutes for the PV system. In the demo, we shared four months of data for each Riello inverter, reflecting the operation of the demo after the LPC deployment and the data collection window for those devices. However, the Tesla system was available for five months after the LPC deployment; hence, the different number of files. Finally, data from the PV field generation at the PCC was available for 12 months after the LPC deployment.

Table 8: UC8, KPI19, services provided via the data spaces.

Name/title of service provided	Category of provided service	Number of files provided
Riello Battery System Operation Data (for INV1)	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	4
Riello Battery System Operation Data (for INV2)	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	4
Riello Battery System Operation Data (for INV3)	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	4
Tesla Battery System Operation Data	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	5
PV Generation Data	Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Meter Data	12

Publishing these files in the data space confirms that the objective of enabling actual data exchange and service deployment was achieved.

3.1.2.9 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was assessed by adding together the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration. The maximum expected capacity was initially set at 3.12 MW, of which 1.5 MW was allocated to the Riello battery, 0.5 MW to the Tesla battery, 1.1 MW to the PV and 0.02 MW to the HP.

During the demonstration phase, all of the planned assets also contributed to the total rated power. Taken together, the integrated assets reached a combined rated power of 3.12 MW, confirming the full achievement of the KPI objective.

3.1.2.10 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI measures the increase in operational flexibility enabled by integrated assets. It is defined as the proportion of unused energy capacity (in MWh) available for flexible services, relative to the total integrated capacity. Unused capacity is calculated by multiplying the stored power not used by the corresponding time, and expressing this value as a percentage of the total nominal capacity set out under KPI3. The maximum expected capacity was 3.025 MWh, of which 0.525 MWh came from the Riello battery and 2.5 MWh from the Tesla battery.

During the demonstration phase, the available capacity was assessed on an hourly basis. The Riello BESS showed an average capacity of 0.49 MWh per hour, equivalent to approximately 99.8% of its nominal value. This high figure is due to its role as a UPS, which required it to be kept close to full charge. The Tesla BESS recorded an average available capacity of 1.53 MWh per hour, which is approximately 58.9% of its nominal capacity. In addition to these two battery systems, the Viessmann heat pump and its thermal energy storage provided a rated capacity of 0.121 MWh, with an average available capacity of 0.055 MWh per hour during the demonstration.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the integrated assets in UC8 achieved an average available capacity equivalent to 68.96% of their total nominal capacity. This confirms that the flexibility potential was quantifiable and was effectively demonstrated under operational conditions, thus validating the KPI.

3.1.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

Here are reported some qualitative insights on the KPI results in UC8:

- **Strengths:** The UC8 demonstration not only met but also exceeded KPI targets, surpassing initial expectations. The results emphasised the robustness and adaptability of the InterSTORE LPC, demonstrating that it is a lightweight and efficient tool. It was successfully deployed on a low-cost single-board computer (SBC), i.e., the RPi, even in scenarios requiring multiple protocol transformations and the integration of multi-physics assets. Furthermore, seamless integration with the commercial EMS was achieved without any technical issues, demonstrating the maturity and reliability of the solution.
- **Deviations:** No major deviations were observed in relation to the planned targets. The few cases where the results did not fully match the expected values were due to operational considerations rather than technical limitations (e.g. the decision not to digitise certain assets, such as the HP and TES, or to not curtail the PV generation). Overall, the UC remained fully aligned with the objectives defined in D5.1 [3].
- **Challenges:** During the pilot phase, asynchronous communication between the Modbus and MQTT components caused difficulties since the EMS algorithm requires synchronised values to operate correctly. This issue was resolved by introducing synchronised readings aligned with a common time server in the latest LPC release. Another practical challenge arose from the large volume of data exchanged during experiments: improper logging configuration in the LPC container could lead to very large log files being generated. This issue was resolved by optimising the logging settings to ensure stable and efficient operation during continuous data flows.
- **Insights:** The demonstration confirmed that standardised communication across heterogeneous DERs can be implemented effectively using lightweight, low-cost and easily scalable solutions. Synchronisation of data streams is essential when multiple protocols and time-sensitive algorithms are running in parallel, highlighting the importance of robust time coordination in such environments. Furthermore, careful attention to system configuration (e.g. logging setup and synchronisation alignment) is vital for ensuring long-term stable operation, and should be considered a best practice for replication. These results highlight the replicability of the approach and offer clear guidance on scaling up the solution for more complex, multi-asset deployments in other frameworks.

Finally, it is worth noticing that the developments and demonstrations activities associated with UC3 led to the following scientific publications:

- [12] D. Liu, D. Carta, A. Xhonneux, D. Müller and A. Benigni, "Short-Term Control of Heat Pumps to Support Power Grid Operation," in *IEEE Open Journal of the Industrial Electronics Society*, vol. 5, pp. 1221-1238, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OJIES.2024.3486560.
- [13] D. Liu, E. De Din, D. Carta and A. Benigni, "Controller Hardware-in-The-Loop Testing of a Multitimescale Control Architecture for Multienergy Systems," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 499-510, April 2025, doi: 10.1109/JESTIE.2025.3546680.
- [11] C. S. Charan Dande *et al.*, "Introduction of Legacy Protocol Converter as an Interoperability Software," *2025 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)*, Valencia, Spain, 2025, pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1109/ICE/ITMC65658.2025.11106664.

4 Portuguese pilot

4.1 Pilot introduction

This Pilot is located in an industrial campus, which has a big variety of energy assets installed as a combined heat and power (CHP) plant, PV systems, different energy storage systems, buildings and EV chargers.

In the demonstration we focused our work on UC 5 (described in this section), involving a hybrid energy storage system located in a building with PV installed on the rooftop, and UC6 (described in 4.3), using a new energy storage system installed next to an EV chargers hub.

The Portuguese demonstration focused on the following elements of the project:

- Deployment of IEEE 2030.5 LPC for monitoring purposes
- Demand response
- Flexibility availability estimation of HESS
- User engagement
- Use of second life battery
- Node capacity increase

4.2 Use case 5 - Hybrid floating storage flexibility monitoring

In this UC, a HESS is installed in a building basement is monitored for optimal hybrid dispatch. The HESS is composed by two batteries. One is a vanadium redox flow battery, with 10kW and 40kWh, and the other is a set of second life lithium batteries with 100kW and 92 kWh. These batteries are connected to their inverters and are operated according to an EMS installed in a local PC. The HESS is connected to the building, 'behind the meter'. The building also has a PV system of 100kW installed on the top.

In the present UC, it is expected to demonstrate strategies for the HESS operation, that aim to optimize a cost function (minimizing the system degradation), comparing hybrid systems to single-battery systems. The UC will also integrate the IEEE 2030.5 LPC in the 2nd life battery inverter/BMS as further explained in D5.2 (implementation, [2]), to showcase the interoperable solution of InterSTORE, applied to distributed resources. The KPIs are assessed according to the corresponding description of Deliverable D5.1 (KPI planning, [3]).

4.2.1 What Has Been Implemented

The actual implementation at the pilot site and assets relevant for the KPI evaluation are the following:

- Technologies deployed: two batteries; lithium-ion and Vanadium redox types (vanadium redox flow battery, VRFB) and corresponding inverters. The inverters communicated via Modbus with the local PC.
- Software tools integrated: IEEE 2030.5 LPC, NATS server, Hybrid energy management systems (HEMS) microservices (forecast module and HESS battery dispatch, etc.).
- Demonstration actions performed: inverter measurements and building consumption/generation data were input to the HEMS. The HEMS produced a forecast for the following day and based on it, it provided the optimal dispatch for two objectives:
 - cost minimization
 - average emissions minimization.

It then estimated the flexibility availability of the battery systems assuming it was dispatched as instructed. The communications of one inverter were done using the IEEE 2030.5 LPC at the BMS side on a local personal computer (PC) using running LabView controller.

4.2.2 KPI Evaluation

INESCTEC provided daily the forecasts and the dispatch recommendations for the HESS based on the model developed including generic tech degradation curves [14]. These were setpoints provided for the day-ahead operation, placed on a common database created to exchange data with CapWatt, so that a record of the files existed and for easy access by both parties. The demonstration lasted for 10 months in total, after which the files were analyzed and the KPIs were calculated and further identified in Table 9 here after.

Table 9: UC5, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0,2	0,13	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	1	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	4	Achieved
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	20	1	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	1	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50%	100%	Achieved
17	Data Valorisation cases	4	4	Achieved
18	HESS performance	20%	21%	Achieved
19	Data Spaces	20	2644 (files)	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	0.222 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	69,23%	Achieved

4.2.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, which is expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the aggregated value in the Portuguese UC 5 demo was 0,13 MWh, comprising 0.04 MWh from the VisBlue VRF battery and 0,09 MWh from the BeePlanet 2nd Life Battery. During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated into the industrial EMS, for optimization and flexibility availability estimation. These values are confirmed by the equipment Specific datasheet.

4.2.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were either tested, monitored or controlled within the Portuguese pilot scheme for UC 5. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each DER counted as one unit if it was tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested or monitored. None of the assets were controlled in this case. The following assets were monitored: Building 4A Load, PV 4A Generation, VisBlue VRF, BeePlanet 2nd Life Battery, The datasets of sample operations were provided as proof for each type of asset.

4.2.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored or data used by the HEMS microservices via the InterSTORE integration in UC 5. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration is counted individually. The following assets were counted: Building 4A Load, PV 4A Generation, VisBlue VRF, BeePlanet 2nd Life Battery. All assets datasets as samples of operation are provided as proof of KPI achievement. This outcome demonstrates the robustness and scalability of the InterSTORE framework in enabling comprehensive asset monitoring via the HEMS.

4.2.2.4 KPI 7 – Number of end users in-volved in HESS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of end users (workers, EV users, consumers) engaged in the demonstration of interoperable HESS. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration is counted individually. Two types of users were considered:

- the building 4A Users (passive users) which are the actual workers reaching 150 that are the responsables for the building load consumption;
- the HESS Owner (Beeplanet and Visblue batteries), assets owner, which is CapWatt and counts as 1.

4.2.2.5 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

The Portuguese pilot contributed to this KPI with the Ingeteam Inverter allocated to the BeePlanet Lithium-ion Battery. The LPC was deployed on a local PC.

4.2.2.6 KPI 11 – Data space digitized assets

This KPI measured the number of assets integrated into the common data space that were actively exchanging data. To ensure consistency, only assets defined under KPI 5 (see 4.2.2.3) were considered, on the condition that each asset transmitted data to the data space at least once. The digitalized assets were the following:

- PV 4A providing PV Generation from roof-top installation;
- VisBlue VRF Vanadium battery;
- BeePlanet 2nd Life Battery;
- Sentinel Platform; - digital Platform providing several sets of datasets such as emissions, prices, weather.

4.2.2.7 KPI 17 – Data Valorisation cases

This KPI evaluates the extent to which shared data can be used in modelling activities to provide added-value services. In this regard, INESC TEC developed 4 valorisation cases:

- PV Performance Evaluation Tool;
- HESS optimal dispatch tool;
- Green EV charging Ranking tool;
- Battery anomaly detection model.

All services were made available through the project repository on GitHub [15], and the shared data from the pilots plus the complementary data provided by INESC TEC, allowed the use of all the models. The data exchanged were provided by the project created data space, incorporating the new improvements to the connector made by Engineering. In particular the anomaly detection was a developed model in the projects and opensource published [16].

4.2.2.8 KPI 18 – HESS performance

The HESS optimal dispatch resulted from a cost optimization model for operation provided by INESC TEC. This algorithm took into account the energy prices for the next day, the forecast of the associated building load and the characteristics of the battery, including degradation. This dispatch was provided to CAPWATT every day in a time series with setpoints, considering daily dispatches. The cost associated of this dispatch was compared to the cost of the actual dispatch followed by CAPWATT. Two days were considered as samples to provide the comparison:

one from November 2024 with an average price of optimal dispatch of 0.090065 compared to an average price of the dispatch followed of 0.111525, which is about 19% lower.

li) the second example is for a day in November with an average price of optimal dispatch of 0.047931 compared to an average price of the dispatch followed of 0.062149, which is about 23% lower, hence, both confirming a lower cost.

4.2.2.9 KPI 19 – Data Spaces

This KPI is evaluated based on the total number of services and associated files that have been subscribed to and published within all the demonstrations. The Portuguese pilot contributed with not only the assets related data (battery operation, solar generation, building load and EV charging data) but also with complementary data from INESC TEC such as CO₂ emissions per pilot zone, Day-ahead market prices per pilot zone, HESS flexibility availability and Weather forecast data for Portugal. All of each corresponding datasets were included in folders/services and the number of datasets were counted after the demonstration period (and may differ from the ones presented here as the demos keep running). The number of files can be checked from the connector UI in each of the services, and printscreens of these are provided as confirmation.

4.2.2.10 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the sum of the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration. The UC 5 was comprised of 2 battery systems with different technologies for hybrid energy storage system related work. During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated and the maximum rated power of 0.132 MW was achieved as planned. The individual integrated capacities were of the Visblue battery with 0.04 MW and of the BeePlanet battery with 0.092 MW. The corresponding technical data sheets provided attest for these contributions.

4.2.2.11 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI evaluates the increase in operational flexibility made possible by the integrated assets. It is calculated as the sum of the unused energy capacity (expressed in MWh) available for flexible services, relative to the total integrated capacity. Available capacity is derived by multiplying unused stored power by the corresponding time, and is then expressed as a percentage of the total capacity defined under KPI3 (see 4.2.2.1). In UC 5 the HESS (Beeplanet and Visblue Batteries) was used for assessing flexibility availability every day. The rated capacity [MW] was 0.13 and the Available energy [average MWh/time] was 0.05. The time step provided was Hourly every day, and the Available capacity/energy [average MWh/time] assessed was 38.46. A sample file is provided as proof of KPI achievement.

4.2.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

Overall the demonstration proved and achieved the objectives. The following points can be highlighted:

- **Strengths:** The optimal dispatch of the HESS was performed. The local LPC deployment on the local PC was straightforward and the variables were monitored without any difficulties. The access to data from the industrial partner, facilitated the development of the anomaly detection model and the Hybrid storage sizing model [17] made available open-source.
- **Deviations:** The VRFB part of the HESS was out of order frequently which disrupted the comparison in a larger time window without interruptions. However the comparison was able to be done. The CO2 differences was not done since when investigated the correct way of doing it, the marginal values should have been taken into consideration instead of average ones and the lack of a baseline did not made it possible to perform an accurate calculation.
- **Challenges:** Regarding the cost reduction and emissions (KPI18, see 4.2.2.8) despite having a sufficiently large time window of analysis, this KPI was hindered due to the fact that the Vanadium battery was out of operation for malfunctioning/maintenance purposes. The HESS dispatch could not be followed and hence the choice of comparison of running a HESS dispatch with single dispatch was followed considering the theoretical optimization dispatch provided by INESC TEC with the actual dispatch performed by CAPWATT with the Li-ion battery. The cost was reported to be using day samples with an average of 20% cost reduction. Such reduction was as expected since an optimal dispatch is always better than some other battery service (even maximizing auto-consumption). Regarding the emissions calculation, it was not possible to estimate, for two reasons. The first is that the majority of the self-consumption resulted is such low values of average emissions throughout the day, that when compared to the optimal dispatch it did not render any significant improvement. The second reason is that for demand response emissions avoidance calculation, the marginal value of emissions should be used instead of the average ones¹, for which the baseline is missing. Nevertheless, the goal of the KPI assessment was to demonstrate a superior performance (at least in terms of cost), which ended up being demonstrated.
- **Insights:** The optimal dispatch of the batteries in terms of cost is always a baseline to be followed and the best approach for controlling the system unless other objectives are required. The fact that the VRFB was frequently out of order did not allow for a straightforward baseline comparison. We have observed that degradation does not play a significant role in the dispatch of the batteries. In fact, the verified cost of degradation was practically offset by the difference in efficiency between the technologies.

Finally, it is worth noticing that the developments and demonstrations activities associated with UC3 led to the following scientific publications:

- [14] M. Preto, A. Lucas, and P. Benedicto, "Hybrid Energy Storage System Dispatch Optimization for Cost and Environmental Impact Analysis," *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 12, p. 2987, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.3390/en17122987.
- [16] A. Lucas, S. Carvalhosa and S. Golmaryami, "Gaussian Mixture Model for Battery Operation Anomaly Detection," *2024 International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies (SEST)*, Torino, Italy, 2024, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/SEST61601.2024.10694471
- [17] A. Lucas, S. Golmaryami, and S. Carvalhosa, "Hybrid Energy Storage System sizing model based on load recurring pattern identification," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 91, p. 112134, June 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2024.112134.

¹ <https://www.electricitymaps.com/content/marginal-vs-average-real-time-decision-making>

4.3 Use case 6 - Management of battery systems for Node capacity increase

This use case was demonstrated in the Sonae Capital car parking lot with an EV charging infrastructure expanded during the project. This UC aimed to demonstrate how an BESS can contribute to the increase of the power capacity for short periods, of the parking lot node according to the needs, enabling the operation of power demands (from an expansion of the EV infrastructure) above the upstream power limitation of the installation. This avoided the refurbishment investment in infrastructures, from increasing the capacity of upstream cables, electrical boards and transformer.

The controlling system of this UC is able to analyze the load of the electrical switchboard, the load of the chargers and the BESS condition status, in order to provide information for limit power of each EV charger.

Another element of this UC, was the study of the EV users themselves and the willingness to participate in a demand response programme. The users received an environmental signal in CO₂/kWh to deviate from their baseline. The deviation assessment was calculated in the backend by INESC TEC. The incentives were provided to the consumers for the demonstration purposes, through a dedicated TEAMS chat. An initial survey and a final one were conducted to help identify the preferred options for inventive communication and willingness to participate and also perception of DR incentive mechanisms.

4.3.1 What Has Been Implemented

For the two studies in this UC (storage for EV parking lot support and EV DR assessment, different tools were used and deployed:

- Technologies deployed (Parking lot battery and EV chargers.)
- Software tools integrated (EMS providing incentives through Microsoft TEAMS)
- Demonstration actions performed (DR assessment, incentive provision, monitoring of the support battery in improving the simultaneity factor of charging sessions etc.)

4.3.2 KPI Evaluation

Bellow the different contributions to specific and overall project KPIs

Table 10: UC6, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.2	0.045	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	10	Achieved
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	20	32	Achieved
20	User Engagement	20%	55%	Achieved
21	Demand Response	6 kWh	10.75 kWh/day average	Achieved
22	Node power increase time	60 min/workday	73 min/workday	Achieved
23	Node power increase percentage	5%	19.4%	Achieved
24	User participation	10%	15%	Achieved

25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	0.09 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	100%	Achieved

4.3.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, which is expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the aggregated value in the Portuguese UC 6 demo was 0.045 MWh, comprising the Huawei Battery. This value is confirmed by the equipment Specific datasheet.

4.3.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were either tested, monitored or controlled within the Portuguese pilot scheme for UC 6. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each DER counted as one unit if it was tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested or monitored. None of the assets were controlled in this case. The following assets were monitored:

- EV charger 1 - Efacec 7.4 kW;
- EV charger 2 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 3 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 4 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 5 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 6 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 7 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 8 - Circutor 2x7.4; (2 sockets with 7,4kW max output each)
- EV charger 9 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 10 - Efacec 160. (Ultra fast charger with 160 kW max output socket)

The datasets of sample operations were provided as proof for each type of asset.

4.3.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored or data used by the HEMS microservices via the InterSTORE integration in UC 6. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration is counted individually. The following assets were counted:

- EV charger 1 - Efacec 7.4 kW;
- EV charger 2 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 3 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 4 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 5 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 6 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 7 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 8 - Circutor 2x7.4; (2 sockets with 7,4kW max output each)
- EV charger 9 - Alfen 2x22; (2 sockets with 22kW max output each)
- EV charger 10 - Efacec 160. (Ultra fast charger with 160 kW max output socket)

All assets datasets as samples of operation are provided as proof of KPI achievement. This outcome demonstrates the robustness and scalability of the InterSTORE framework in enabling comprehensive asset monitoring via the HEMS.

4.3.2.4 KPI 7 – Number of end users involved in HESS

This KPI was assessed focusing on the EV users that participated in the DR campaign. The users filled out surveys, received incentives everyday and decided if they wanted to adjust their charging behaviour. 32 Users were recruited and involved in the experiment.

4.3.2.5 KPI 20 – User Engagement

This KPI was assessed thanks to the surveys conducted with the EV user group. This intended to assess the improved acceptance and perception by end users towards a participation in DR schemes. A set of surveys were made available and answered start and end of demo. A specific question (question 13) was exactly this. The aggregated responses from the users were: 55% Partial they would be willing to change vs 100% said they would or maybe change. This can be seen in question 13 and 5 of the initial/final surveys. Both available as pdfs.

4.3.2.6 KPI 21 – Demand Response

In this KPI we considered the top 3 users (i.e., with user ID: ID76, ID50, and ID35), which we observed a positive correlation between the change in behaviour and the provided incentives. A sample day for each was chosen, the 26, 27 and 20th of March 2024 respectively and the corresponding energy of the charging session on that day was retrieved. This energy is considered the shifted amount due to the incentive provision, and is hence the avoided energy in the non-incentive scenario.

4.3.2.7 KPI 22 – Node power increase time

This KPI was calculated for a 44 days data analysis, where the battery was programmed to limit the node power capacity to 150 kW, and we measured the time above this limit that the battery was used during this demonstration.

We were able to calculate that in this test, the battery was discharged during 2335 minutes in 32 workdays, which means that the battery has worked for 73 min/workday in order to support the power demand above the 150 kW limit.

4.3.2.8 KPI 23 – Node power increase percentage

This KPI was calculated comparing the maximum register of peak power demand in that grid node, that was 232.1 kW, with the real battery power available for discharge and reduce the peak power, that is 45 kW. This represents a maximum percentage of 19.4% ($45/232.1$), of Power surpassing the installation's capacity.

4.3.2.9 KPI 24 – User participation

This KPI was calculated as a percentage of users (being monitored), actively following the DR incentive. Actively meaning that they follow the incentive (deviate from past behaviour) on the majority of days during the demonstration. In total there were 5 users which has a positive correlation with the incentives provided. In fact, three with positive correlation with the change in behaviour, i.e., when they changed their behaviour they did it in the same direction on the incentives provided, plus two other users that despite not having had changes observed, they did not because they were already aligned with the provided incentives. In total 32 EV users were part of the campaign (receiving the information with the incentives), and only 5 were actively aligned with the incentive corresponding to 15.6% ($5/32$).

4.3.2.10 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the sum of the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration. The UC 6, the storage asset considered was the Huawei battery providing support to the EV charging parking lot. During the demonstration phase, the asset had its full power available and successfully integrated with maximum rated power of 0.09 MW and achieved as planned. The corresponding technical data sheets provided attest for these contributions. The integrated capacity of the Huawei battery was 0.09 MW

4.3.2.11 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI evaluates the increase in operational flexibility made possible by the integrated assets. It is calculated as the sum of the unused energy capacity (expressed in MWh) available for flexible services, in this case for supporting the EV charging sessions, or provide services to the grid. In this case it was 0.045 MW, corresponding to 0.045 MWh in an hour, being capable of in fact discharging/charging 0.09 MWh.

4.3.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

This UC had different outcomes and several remarks are worth highlighting:

- **Strengths:** The battery supporting the EV charging sessions worked without any problems. The EV users participation in the survey was high and perception increase was verified. The use case provided the ideal set to the development of a battery control algorithm and to develop the methodology to evaluate the consumer response to incentives by correlation analysis.
- **Deviations:** No deviations occurred, except the way in which the DR was calculated. Initially the response from the users was expected to be compared to a baseline based on a forecast for the charging sessions. However such forecast attempt was of very low accuracy and a correlation between changes (from historical patterns) and actual sessions was assessed. The target however was achieved for the associated KPI.
- **Challenges:** The correlation assessed between the changes of historical charging sessions to the ones actually observed cannot prove causality, hence this limitation of the study must be highlighted.

For all the KPIs assessed it is worth noting several observations namely regarding the following KPIs:

With regards to user engagement (KPI20, discussed in 4.3.2.5) even though the KPI was reached, the engagement was limited due to a few study limitations. Several users reported not having the possibility to opt for remote control of charging to differ or anticipate the charging session and could not leave their jobs to do so manually. Another aspect reported was that, even if users had availability to change manually their charging sessions, the number of charger were in such number that low availability was observed, limiting the time windows options that a user had to charge.

Regarding the actual demand response value (KPI21, presented in 4.3.2.6) in kWh/day, the top 3 users (ID76, ID50, and ID35) were considered to calculate the KPIs since they were the ones showing positive correlation in changing behavior towards the direction of the incentive provided. 3 sample days were picked and the total energy of each charging event on that day was reported as the energy being shifted to another time window block, resulting in a successful KPI being reached of just (>6kWh/day). The baseline alternative approach was not possible to follow since the accuracy of the charging session forecast being insufficient to be used as a credible comparison basis.

Insights: For DR studies, an actual incentive should be given to the user. In this case the users did not pay for charging the EVs, as they were charging in the company's premises. Even though an environmental one was provided, potential actions were limited by lack of possibility to practically change manually the charging moment or lack of availability of the charging infrastructure. Moreover, a setup of control and test groups would have been desired, but due to the size of the group this was not possible.

5 Spanish pilot

5.1 Pilot introduction

The Spanish pilot is hosted by HESStec at the GridLab facility, Valencia, which provides a MW scale realistic environment for testing hybrid energy storage systems (HES) in grid-support applications. The laboratory combines a high-power grid-forming converter, a lithium-ion battery system, and an ultracapacitor module, all coordinated by the HyDEMS EMS platform. Within InterSTORE, the Spanish pilot had a dual objective: to demonstrate how hybrid storage can deliver innovative frequency services and support autonomous grid operation, and to validate the deployment of advanced EMS with State of Function (SoF) algorithm incorporating interoperability tools (LPC and IEEE 2030.5 over NATS) in such a demanding control environment.

The pilot addressed two use cases: UC4 (Innovative Frequency Services) and UC7 (Adaptive BESS management for autonomous grid operation). Both required sub-second response and seamless integration between the EMS, storage assets, and aggregator interfaces.

5.2 Use case 4 - Innovative Frequency services

Implementation

In UC4, the HES was configured to provide services such as Fast Frequency Response (FFR), synthetic inertia, and Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR). The ultracapacitor ensured rapid power injection/absorption during the first instants of frequency deviations, while the battery provided sustained energy delivery. Interoperability tools were deployed as defined in Deliverable D3.3 [1], [5], following option 3.3: a local LPC and NATS on a dedicated server enabled low-latency EMS-device communication, while a second NATS instance in the cloud supported aggregator integration.

5.2.1 What Has Been Implemented

The control architecture followed deployment option 3.3, as defined in Deliverable D3.3 – Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Platforms [1], [5]. In this configuration, a single LPC and a local NATS message broker were deployed on a dedicated industrial server within the local network. The LPC handled the bidirectional translation between the Modbus TCP protocol used by the power converter and storage controllers, and the IEEE 2030.5 / XML data model required by HyDEMS. The local NATS instance ensured low-latency publish/subscribe communication between the EMS and the LPC. HyDEMS has been updated with development of SoF and hybridization algorithms for incorporation of different assets such as:

- Grid forming (GFM) Danfoss converter, in the following denoted as DER1
- Grid Following (GFL) converter, in the following denoted as DER2
- Grid Emulator
- Ultracapacitors (UCAPs) with their management tool
- Batteries with its Battery Management System (BMS).

The LPC and NATS components were containerized and deployed using Docker Compose, as described in D3.3 [1], [5] and D5.2 [2]. The setup consisted of three coordinated containers:

- LPC container running the InterSTORE-developed protocol translation service with IEEE 2030.5 client/server capabilities.
- Local NATS container acting as the messaging bus for real-time telemetry and commands between EMS and LPC.
- Node-RED container used for commissioning, debugging, and real-time data visualization during testing.

The implemented system enabled testing of different services such as:

- Fast Frequency Response (FFR)
- Synthetic inertia
- Peak shaving
- Firming

During the tests, intentional frequency disturbances were applied to emulate grid events, allowing evaluation of the dynamic response of the hybrid system and the communication latency of the interoperability chain. Results demonstrated that the full local control loop, from HyDEMS command to converter action, operated with a mean delay below 250 ms, validating the suitability of the chosen architecture for sub-second frequency support.

5.2.2 KPI Evaluation

Specific KPIs for Spanish pilot use cases are focused on time data savings (KPI 12), monitoring (KPI 13), response time (KPI 14), frequency stability (KPI 15) – NADIR, (KPI 16) – ROCOF) and Tests confirmed that the hybrid system reached response times of around 250 ms, with the ultracapacitor handling fast dynamics and the battery ensuring longer stability. Data were fully monitored through HyDEMS through the LPC, and standardised IEEE 2030.5 messages improved availability compared to Modbus polling.

Table 11: UC4, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.2 MWh	0.205 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	2.5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	2	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	1	Achieved
12	Time data savings	250 ms	200 ms	Achieved
13	Monitoring	2	3	Achieved
14	Time response	0.5 s	0.25 s	Achieved
15	System NADIR	49.5 Hz	49.7 Hz	Achieved
16	System ROCOF	2 Hz/s	0.9 Hz/s	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	0.5 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	90%	Achieved

5.2.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

As previously explained, this KPI was assessed based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). The maximum expected value was defined as 0.205 MWh, consisting of 0.2 MWh from the battery pack and 0.005 MWh from the UCAP within the HESS system. During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated into the DER1-GFM to enable the deployment of the software tool, which provided various fast and slow functionalities for UC4 and UC7 (see 5.3.2.1).

5.2.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by summing the number of DERs that were both tested and controlled within the Spanish grid lab. In this case, each DER counted as one unit if it was both tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested (or just monitored). Therefore, for Spanish pilot two DER, DER1 GFM, and Grid emulator has been controller and monitored. While DER2-GFL has been monitored only. This will be counted as 2.5 as contribution of Spanish pilot to the main target of the project. This units have been used for both UC4 and UC7 (see 5.3.2.2) during tests and demonstration of the project.

5.2.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

As mentioned, this KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored by Spanish EMS in advanced grid lab during demonstration phase of the project. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration was counted individually. In this case two units has been monitored independently, which are DER1-GFM and DER2-GFL. Therefore the contribution of this pilot respect to the total target is 2 for both UC4 and UC7 (see 5.3.2.3).

5.2.2.4 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

As explained this KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were successfully integrated using the IEEE 2030.5 standard and enabled via the LPC. This was demonstrated in advanced grid lab of Spanish pilot with different testing conditions. In this pilot DRE1-GFM as the main played has been used and deployed successfully for both UC4 and UC7 (see 5.3.2.4).

5.2.2.5 KPI 12 – Time data saving

This KPI was evaluated during the demonstration phase of the Spanish pilot, primarily within the fast frequency service tests conducted under UC4. It measures the time needed in data acquisition and transmission time between the HESS and the HyDEMS EMS for providing fast services when using the InterSTORE interoperability tools compared to the traditional Modbus-based approach.

This KPI was evaluated during the Virtual Inertia (VI) and Fast Peak Shaving (FPS) tests conducted within UC4. Based on the results obtained at the GridLab facility, three trial tests were performed for the VI service, where the average time using the conventional approach was approximately 100 ms, while the InterSTORE method using the LPC achieved an average of 150 ms. For the FPS service, ten trial tests were carried out, showing an average time of 150 ms with the Modbus-based setup and 250 ms with the InterSTORE approach. In both cases, the measured performance remained well within the acceptable limits for fast-response grid services, confirming that the interoperability layer introduced by the LPC does not compromise the dynamic performance of the system.

5.2.2.6 KPI 13 – Monitoring

This KPI assesses the real-time monitoring capability of the InterSTORE framework for DERs at the GridLab facility. It was evaluated focusing on the Grid-Forming DER1, Grid-Following DER2, and the Grid Emulator Converter. During the final tests, all three assets were successfully monitored through the InterSTORE software framework using the LPC and NATS communication layers. Continuous data exchange enabled real-time visibility of voltage, current, power, and SoC parameters, confirming full asset availability and achieving the expected monitoring performance target.

5.2.2.7 KPI 14 – time response

As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], this KPI represents the overall response time of the HESS required to provide grid services in compliance with TSO grid codes. It was evaluated by measuring the total delay and time response between a service request issued by the operator and the full power response from the assets. With target of $T_f = 0.5$ s for fast services and $T_s = 1$ s for slower services. During the final demonstrations, the total response time for fast services such as VI was approximately 0.25 s using the LPC-based InterSTORE approach, while slower services, like Firming Service, achieved a response time of around 0.9 s. In all cases, the performance was within the defined limits and demonstrated improved stability and reliability compared to the conventional Modbus-only configuration.

5.2.2.8 KPI 15 – NADIR

This KPI, as explained in D5.1 [3], represents the lowest frequency value recorded at the point of interconnection (POI) during frequency regulation. It serves as a direct indicator of the system's ability to stabilize frequency deviations during dynamic events. During the final demonstration tests, the frequency signal was continuously monitored, and the NADIR was calculated based on the averaged values obtained. The measured result of 49.7 Hz/s was better than the assigned target, confirming the effective response of the hybrid energy storage system and the capability of the InterSTORE control architecture to maintain frequency stability within required grid code limits.

5.2.2.9 KPI 16 – ROCOF

This KPI represents the rate of change of frequency (df/dt) measured at the POI during the first instants following a disturbance. It was assessed to evaluate the system's dynamic response during fast frequency services. The calculation was performed within a 0.5-second time window after the occurrence of each event, using high-resolution frequency measurements recorded at GridLab. During the final demonstration tests, the measured ROCOF value of 0.9 Hz/s was well below the target threshold of 2 Hz/s, confirming the high stability and rapid response capability of the hybrid energy storage system. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the InterSTORE developments in achieving fast and reliable frequency regulation.

5.2.2.10 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the sum of the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration within the project. The contributed portion from Spanish pilot was 0.5 MW by grid forming DER which in total the expected target has been achieved in the project.

5.2.2.11 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI evaluates the increase in operational flexibility made possible by the integrated assets. It is calculated as the sum of the unused energy capacity (expressed in MWh) available for flexible services, relative to the total integrated capacity.

Spanish pilot was able to contribute by a 0.45 average MWh within the project by a GFM DER with its rated capacity of 0.5 MW.

5.2.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

The results of UC4 confirmed the strong capability of the hybrid energy storage system to deliver fast dynamic services such as Virtual Inertia (VI) and Fast Peak Shaving (FPS). The measured KPIs demonstrated that all key performance targets were achieved: time response remained within 0.5 s, ROCOF and NADIR indicators stayed well below their thresholds, and

full asset monitoring was maintained through the InterSTORE software framework. The combination of the ultracapacitor for immediate response and the battery for sustained support proved highly effective, enhancing system stability while reducing stress on individual components.

A notable strength of the implementation was the stability and robustness of the communication chain based on the LPC and dual NATS architecture, which ensured deterministic data delivery even during rapid service activation. The main challenge encountered was fine-tuning the coordination between fast and slow control loops within HyDEMS to avoid transient overshoots in power exchange. Minor deviations in time-response values between the conventional and LPC methods were observed but remained within acceptable margins and did not affect service quality. Overall, the pilot validated that the InterSTORE interoperability framework can deliver fast frequency-related services with high reliability and standard-compliant performance.

As Use Case 4 was dedicated to fast services related to frequency regulation and oscillation damping, another important outcome of this task was the acceptance and presentation of a conference paper at a prestigious international event in 2025:

[18] E. Rakhshani, X. Benavides and E. Dominguez, "Power Oscillation Damping Capabilities of Grid Forming Based Hybrid Energy Storage Technology," *2025 IEEE Kiel PowerTech*, Kiel, Germany, 2025, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/PowerTech59965.2025.11180635.

5.3 Use case 7 - Adaptive BESS management for autonomous grid operation

UC7 extended the validation of UC4, presented in Section 5.2, to black-start and islanding scenarios. The EMS was programmed to adaptively manage the BESS, reallocating setpoints in real time depending on SoC and system conditions. The LPC allowed Modbus-based controllers to interoperate with IEEE 2030.5, enabling HyDEMS to coordinate devices seamlessly. Again, the dual NATS architecture provided resilience: the local NATS ensured continued operation in islanded mode, while the cloud NATS supported aggregator interaction when connectivity was available.

5.3.1 What Has Been Implemented

The main objective was to validate how HyDEMS can autonomously maintain local grid stability and optimize resource utilization under variable operating conditions, while preserving interoperability with higher-level platforms through the InterSTORE software tools. The system architecture again followed deployment option 3.3, as defined in Deliverable D3.3 [1], [5], with the LPC and local NATS server running on a dedicated local server.

The LPC acted as the interface between legacy Modbus TCP devices (battery, UCAP, converter, UCAP controller) and the IEEE 2030.5-compliant HyDEMS EMS. All data exchanged between the devices and the EMS (such as SoC, voltage, power, temperature, and control setpoints) were converted by the LPC into standardised IEEE 2030.5 messages. The local NATS broker managed high-speed message routing within the LAN, ensuring deterministic communication in autonomous operation.

The developed EMS was updated with developments SoF and hybridization algorithms for incorporation of different assets such as:

- Grid forming Danfoss converter, in the following denoted as DRE1
- GFL converter, in the following denoted as DER2
- Grid Emulator
- UCAPs with their management tool
- Batteries with their BMS.

The adaptive control logic implemented in HyDEMS for UC7 was designed to maintain grid frequency and voltage stability during both grid-connected and islanded operation. The EMS incorporated a hierarchical control strategy with three main layers:

1. Fast dynamic control layer: handled transient events such as load steps or frequency deviations, commanding the ultracapacitor to provide instantaneous active power support. This layer operated with response times under 200 ms.
2. Energy balancing layer: dynamically adjusted the battery's active and reactive power setpoints based on the ultracapacitor's SoC, ensuring sustained operation and optimal energy distribution.
3. Adaptive optimisation layer: monitored system conditions, including SoF status, SoC limits, converter loading, and communication status, to switch between grid-connected, islanded, and black-start modes automatically.

In islanded operation, HyDEMS operated in grid-forming mode, managing voltage and frequency references internally. During black-start testing, the EMS initiated the sequence autonomously: the ultracapacitor provided the initial power injection to start the converter, and once stable operation was achieved, the battery took over to supply the base load. The entire process—from trigger to stable local grid formation—was completed within seconds, meeting the requirements defined in D5.1 [3].

The performance of the system was validated through multiple test scenarios, including:

- Black-start and Energization: verification of converter startup and stable local voltage/frequency formation.
- Intentional islanding: transition from grid-connected to autonomous mode without service interruption.
- Resynchronization and reconnection to grid: synchronization and resynchronization processes validated with smooth transitions.
- Voltage Dip Detection and Automatic Transfer Switch (ATS) test: Real-time voltage dip detection and automatic reconfiguration using ATS were assessed under diverse disturbance scenarios.

Data logs collected from HyDEMS confirmed communication latency below 300 ms, even under increased telemetry loads, and full continuity of data exchange via the local NATS broker.

5.3.2 KPI Evaluation

Specific KPIs for Spanish pilot use cases are focused on time data savings (KPI 12), monitoring (KPI 13), response time (KPI 14), frequency stability (KPI 15) – NADIR, (KPI 16) – ROCOF) and Tests confirmed that the hybrid system reached response times of around 250 ms, with the ultracapacitor handling fast dynamics and the battery ensuring longer stability. Data were fully monitored by HyDEMS through the LPC, and standardised IEEE 2030.5 messages improved availability compared to Modbus polling.

Table 12: UC7, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.2 MWh	0.205 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	2.5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	2	Achieved

10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	1	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50%	100%	Achieved
12	Time data savings	250 ms	200 ms	Achieved
13	Monitoring	2	3	Achieved
14	Time response	0.5 s	0.105 s	Achieved
15	System NADIR	49.5 Hz	49.7 Hz	Achieved
16	System ROCOF	2 Hz/s	0.9 Hz/s	Achieved
25	Integrated capacity	1 MW	0.5 MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	90%	Achieved

5.3.2.1 KPI 3 – Battery capacity

This KPI was assessed based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). The maximum expected value was defined as 0.205 MWh, consisting of 0.2 MWh from the battery pack and 0.005 MWh from the UCAP within the HESS system. During the demonstration phase, both assets were successfully integrated into the DER1-GFM to enable the deployment of the software tool, which provided various fast and slow functionalities for UC4 (see 5.2.2.1) and UC7.

5.3.2.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by summing the number of DERs that were both tested and controlled within the Spanish grid lab. In this case, each DER counted as one unit if it was both tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested (or just monitored). Therefore, for Spanish pilot two DER, DER1 GFM, and Grid emulator has been controller and monitored. While DER2-GFL has been monitored only. This will be counted as 2.5 as contribution of Spanish pilot to the main target of the project. This units have been used for both UC4 (see 5.2.2.2) and UC7 during tests and demonstration of the project.

5.3.2.3 KPI 5 – Asset management monitored by EMS

As mentioned, this KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored by Spanish EMS in advanced grid lab during demonstration phase of the project. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration was counted individually. In this case two units has been monitored independently, which are DER1-GFM and DER2-GFL. Therefore the contribution of this pilot respect to the total target is 2 for both UC4 (see 5.2.2.3) and UC7.

5.3.2.4 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

As explained this KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were successfully integrated using the IEEE 2030.5 standard and enabled via the LPC. This was demonstrated in advanced grid lab of Spanish pilot with different testing conditions. In this pilot DRE1-GFM as the main played has been used and deployed successfully for both UC4 (see 5.2.2.4) and UC7.

5.3.2.5 KPI 11 – Data space digitized as-sets

KPI 11 assesses the number of assets integrated into a common data space and actively exchanging data. In the Spanish pilot, the data space concept was prepared and functionally tested. However, due to the specific conditions of UC7 within the platform, the data space was represented only through command signals received from the TSO on top, requesting different grid services.

Accordingly, the entire developed unit was deployed to demonstrate its capability to provide various grid services, effectively validating the potential for future integration with a full data space layer.

5.3.2.6 KPI 12 – Time data saving

Similar to previous use case, reported in 5.2.2.5, this KPI was evaluated during the different fast service test such as voltage dip and synchronization within UC7. Based on the results obtained at the GridLab facility, the average time using the InterSTORE method with the LPC achieved an average around 250 ms. The measured performance remained well within the acceptable limits for fast-response grid services, confirming that the InterSTORE approach by the LPC which are within the acceptable range.

5.3.2.7 KPI 13 – Monitoring

This KPI assesses the real-time monitoring capability of the InterSTORE framework for DERs at the GridLab facility. It was evaluated focusing on the Grid-Forming DER1, Grid-Following DER2, and the Grid Emulator Converter. During the final tests, all three assets were successfully monitored through the InterSTORE software framework using the LPC and NATS communication layers. Continuous data exchange enabled real-time visibility of voltage, current, power, and SoC parameters, confirming full asset availability and achieving the expected monitoring performance target.

5.3.2.8 KPI 14 – Time response

As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], this KPI represents the overall response time of the HESS required to provide grid services in compliance with TSO grid codes. It was evaluated in UC7 by measuring the total delay and time response between a service request issued by the operator and the full power response from the assets. With target of $T_f = 0.5$ s for fast services and $T_s = 1$ s for slower services.

During the final demonstrations, the total response time for fast services in UC7 such as voltage dip, ATS test and synchronization was approximately 0.105 s using the LPC-based InterSTORE approach, while slower services like Firming Service achieved a response time of around 0.9 s. In all cases, the performance was within the defined limits and demonstrated improved stability and reliability compared to the conventional Modbus-only configuration.

5.3.2.9 KPI 15 – NADIR

As stated in the tests described for UC4, in 5.2.2.8, this KPI measures the lowest frequency value at the POI during regulation events. In the UC7 demonstrations, similar monitoring was carried out, and the recorded NADIR of 49.7 Hz/s remained better than the defined target.

5.3.2.10 KPI 16 – ROCOF

As evaluated in the UC4, presented in 5.2.2.9, this KPI measures the rate of change of frequency (df/dt) at the POI immediately after a disturbance. The results showed an average ROCOF of 0.9 Hz/s, well below the target limit of 2 Hz/s, confirming the fast and stable dynamic behaviour of the hybrid energy storage system during autonomous operation.

5.3.2.11 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the sum of the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration within the project. The contributed portion from Spanish pilot was 0.5 MW by grid forming DER which in total the expected target has been achieved in the project.

5.3.2.12 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI evaluates the increase in operational flexibility made possible by the integrated assets. It is calculated as the sum of the unused energy capacity (expressed in MWh) available for flexible services, relative to the total integrated capacity.

Spanish pilot was able to contribute by a 0.45 average MWh within the project by a GFM DER with its rated capacity of 0.5 MW.

5.3.3 Comments and Lessons Learned

The UC7 tests focused on real life contingencies by mixture of fast and slow functionalities, including voltage-dip support, firming, black-start operation, and synchronization using the ATS switch. The KPI results confirmed that the system met all operational targets, maintaining stable frequency and voltage under both connected and islanded conditions. Time response for firming services was within 1 s, NADIR and ROCOF values indicated strong dynamic control, and monitoring via the InterSTORE software framework ensured full observability of all devices.

Key strengths included the action of SoF with hybridization and real time monitoring of different DERS within the HyDEMS platform, which dynamically coordinated the battery and ultracapacitor to restore grid stability after disturbances, and the reliability of the LPC-based communication layer, which remained operational even during network transitions. The black-start and re-synchronization tests highlighted the system's autonomy and ability to restore local power without external commands. Challenges mainly involved ensuring precise SoC estimation during rapid transitions and optimizing the timing of switching actions with the ATS to avoid voltage dips. Despite these complexities, the implementation demonstrated that the InterSTORE approach supports not only fast grid services but also secure and resilient operation under islanded and restoration scenarios.

As the outcome of our activities within this work package and the corresponding use case, two important publications have been achieved:

- [19] J. M. Ruiz, E. Rakhshani, X. Benavides and E. Dominguez, "Synergistic Multi-Service Operation of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems," *2024 12th International Conference on Smart Grid (icSmartGrid)*, Setubal, Portugal, 2024, pp. 469-474, doi: 10.1109/icSmartGrid61824.2024.10578069.
- [20] E. Rakhshani, J. M. Ruiz, X. Benavides and E. Dominguez, "Enhancing Low-Inertia Power Systems with Grid Forming Based Hybrid Energy Storage Technology," *2024 12th International Conference on Smart Grid (icSmartGrid)*, Setubal, Portugal, 2024, pp. 464-468, doi: 10.1109/icSmartGrid61824.2024.10578086.

The second conference publication was selected for the Best Conference Paper Award and recommended for journal publication. Following extensive revisions and extensions during the peer-review process, it has been finally accepted for publication in the prestigious *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications* journal:

- [21] E. Rakhshani, J. M. Ruiz, X. Benavides and E. Dominguez, "Adaptive Interoperable Management of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems for Grid-Forming Services," in *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2025.3634049.

5.3.4 Overall evaluation of the Spanish pilot

The results obtained in the Spanish pilot confirm the effectiveness of the InterSTORE interoperability framework and hybrid energy storage technologies for delivering advanced and resilient grid services. Both use cases, UC4 (Innovative Frequency Services) and UC7 (Adaptive BESS Management for Autonomous Grid Operation), demonstrated that the integration of IEEE 2030.5, through the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) and NATS-based communication, can be successfully implemented in fast, demanding control environments.

Across both demonstrations, all KPIs were met or exceeded. The hybrid storage system achieved sub-second response times, with the ultracapacitor providing rapid active power support and the battery ensuring longer-duration energy delivery. Frequency stability remained within TSO limits, as confirmed by the NADIR and ROCOF results, while the HyDEMS maintained full observability of all subsystems through continuous monitoring and real-time data exchange.

A key insight from the pilot is the crucial role of adaptive EMS logic with incorporation of SoF algorithm in coordinating hybrid assets under dynamic conditions. The ability of HyDEMS to balance the power contribution between the battery and ultracapacitor based on state-of-charge and system needs proved essential for ensuring both stability and component longevity. Minor timing deviations between the conventional Modbus and LPC approaches were observed but remained within acceptable bounds, confirming that the addition of interoperability layers does not compromise performance.

Moreover, as European TSOs increasingly focus on the interoperable operation of DERs with hybridization and grid-forming capabilities, the GridLab facility provided an ideal testing environment to explore such future-oriented requirements. Its flexibility in creating realistic contingencies and service scenarios made it possible to validate the readiness of the InterSTORE developments to contribute to evolving TSO needs and to comply with forthcoming grid code requirements in low-inertia power systems. This reinforces the strategic value of the Spanish pilot, demonstrating that the proposed architecture is not only technically sound but also aligned with the long-term transformation of the European power system.

6 Italian pilot

6.1 Pilot introduction

The Italian pilot's role within InterSTORE is to validate the interoperability and performance of DERs in a varied context, with a particular focus on flexibility services, system reliability, and integration into broader EMS and Flex platforms; in addition enable the aggregation of heterogeneous DERs, including storage systems (industrial, residential, commercial), and electric vehicles, into a unified portfolio capable of delivering meaningful flexibility to the distribution grid. The EnelX role in InterSTORE project is to demonstrate the end-to-end activation of local flexibility services within a simulated environment (XLAB in Rome), replicating real-world grid conditions and interactions between multiple stakeholders, such as Distribution system operator (DSO), Balancing Service Provider (BSP), and Flexibility Platform.

UC9 focuses on identifying and analyzing how various storage technologies, including industrial-scale systems, residential storage, commercial & industrial batteries, and EVs, can be coordinated as a single aggregated cluster to deliver effective flexibility.

The Italian pilot combines advanced research laboratories with real-world testing and demonstration facilities.

The local infrastructure comprises BESS in Industrial, Commercial&Industrial and residential target and different technologies as Supercap battery and Li-ion batteries in different sizes, bifacial PVs with different sizes, and EV chargers V2G CHAdeMO. The Residential battery is integrated with Schneider Conext gateway /XWPRO Product Model 8650330, awarded with IEEE 2030.5 protocol natively implemented on 12/18/2019 accompanied by 2030 CSIP Sun-spect Alliance certification. These DERs assets are all connected with the IT platform: IoT platform, EMS and Flexibility platform to manage Virtual Power Plant (VPP). In InterSTORE, interoperability is ensured through the deployment of the IEEE 2030.5 protocol and the LPC. This setup enables seamless communication between legacy field devices and the standardised control environment.

6.2 Use case 9 - Management of EV charging clusters as HESS

UC9 involves integrating multi physics assets into a Flexibility and EMS framework to improve flexibility and support advanced energy management functions. The objective is to show how different assets, such as a BESS in different size and commercial target and different technologies (supercap and LI-Ion), a PV system and EV-V2G chargers can be seamlessly incorporated into the commercial IoT/EMS/Flex platforms via the LPC and the IEEE 2030.5 protocol and together provide robust and reliable flexibility services to the network.

UC9 contributes to generate insights and recommendations for scaling flexibility services in real distribution networks, supporting the wider integration of renewables and contributing to the energy transition and reinforcing the role of interoperable solutions in enabling smart and flexible grid operations by enabling standardised, real-time data exchange.

Evaluate the use of a flexibility management platform to coordinate, dispatch, and settle flexibility services provided by different types of assets/sites within the BSP's portfolio. Assess the technical and market feasibility of using local ancillary services to meet grid operational needs, while ensuring that small-scale resources can participate effectively through aggregation.

What Has Been Implemented

In the following the relevant implementation for UC9 are listed:

- Technologies deployed (assets, devices, EMS, ICT components, etc.)

- *LAB perimeter*
 - SOCOMEC BESS (Industrial)
 - Greentech SuperCap BESS (Commercial&Industrial)
 - Pylontech Li-Ion BESS (Residential)
 - XWpro Conext Gateway (IEEE 2030.5 Native)
 - High performance Server in Control Room XLAB
 - Bifacial PV 3SUN
 - EV-V2G CHAdEMO
- ENEL Cloud: IT platforms used and SW developed in InterSTORE Prjject
 - IoT platform integration with InterSTORE flows
 - EMS platform (RVXG_ESV4)
 - Algorithms for DERS aggregated Management
 - Flexibility Platform
- Software tools integrated (IEEE 2030.5, LPC, NATS, EMS, etc.)
 - LPC with transformations:
 - Modbus - IEEE 2030.5 - MQTT (monitoring flow)
 - MQTT - IEEE 2030.5 - Modbus (control flow)
 - NATS server
 - IEEE 2030.5 Server integrated with IEEE 2030.5 Client
- Demonstration actions performed (control tests, flexibility dispatch, resilience tests, etc.)
 - Optimization for an Area with Aggregated Assets
 - Asset availability calculation (algorithm)
 - Dis-aggregated dispatching commands calculation (Algorithm)
 - DSO Flexibility DR event: Power set point control

6.2.1 KPI Evaluation

The KPIs evaluated in UC9 are summarized in the table below and detailed in the following sections.

Table 13: UC9, evaluation of the contribution of UC to the overall KPI values.

KPI ID	KPI Name	Target Value (Project level)	Actual Value (UC level)	Status (Achieved / Not)
3	Battery capacity	0.2 MWh	0.2912 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	25	5.5	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	50	8	Achieved
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	20	4	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	10	1.5	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	50%	100%	Achieved
17	Data Valorisation cases	4	4	Achieved
19	Data Spaces	20	25	Achieved

25	Integrated capacity	1 MWh	0.3203MW	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	20%	43.52%	Achieved
27	Energy Volume exchanged	500kWh	1305.05kWh	Achieved
28	Different hybridization configuration	250kW	257kW	Achieved
29	Grid peak avoidance	0.8	0.3932	Achieved

6.2.1.1 KPI 3 – Battery Capacity

For the evaluation of this KPI, the nominal capacity of the integrated assets (expressed in MWh) is considered. The calculated value from battery capacity for flexibility service is 0,2912 MWh.

This KPI was evaluated based on the nominal capacity of the integrated battery assets, which is expressed in megawatt-hours (MWh). As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], the maximum expected value was 0,3 MWh, we have reached it with Large Battery Socomec 0,274 MWh, Medium battery Supercap Greentech 0,0076 MWh and Small Battery Pylontech 0,0096 MWh.

6.2.1.2 KPI 4 – Diversity of DER

This KPI was evaluated by summing the number of DERs that were both tested and controlled within the Italian pilot. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each DER counted as 1 unit if it was both tested and controlled, and as 0.5 if it was only tested (or just monitored). In the Italian pilot, 3 Batteries were tested, integrated and controlled while 1 CHAdeMO EV-V2G charger, and the 3 PV were just tested and monitored.

6.2.1.3 KPI 5 – Asset Management Monitored by EMS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of assets monitored by ESV4 EMS via the InterSTORE integration. As defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3], each integration is counted individually. For the 3 battery system, 3 PV system and 2 EVs V2G chargers resulting in a total of 8 integrations.

6.2.1.4 KPI 7 – Number of End-Users involved in HESS

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of users actively involved in controlling and managing DERs at the Italian pilot site. According to Deliverable D5.1 [3], the expected value was 4: 3 asset owners of the PV and battery systems; and 1 EV user.

However, during the demonstration phase, these users were distributed across different categories of stakeholders, including asset owners, system operators and consumers.

- Asset owners: PV+ Residential BESS(1), PV+ Commercial&Industrial BESS (1), PV+ Industrial BESS (1).
- EV users: 1

6.2.1.5 KPI 10 – Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5

This KPI was evaluated by counting the number of DERs that were successfully integrated using the IEEE 2030.5 standard and enabled via the InterSTORE LPC. This was demonstrated in real-life pilot conditions.

The storages devices that were successfully tested for interoperability, and controllable assets previously tested with their native protocol (e.g. Modbus) were also successfully controlled via IEEE 2030.5.

6.2.1.6 KPI 11 – Data space digitised assets

This KPI evaluated the number of assets integrated into the common data space and actively exchanging data. For consistency, 8 out of 8 assets considered under KPI5, see 6.2.1.3, are accounted for, with the condition that each must send data to the data space at least once. The maximum expected value corresponds to 100%, meaning that all (8) integrated assets achieve digitalization and data exchange.

During the demonstration phase, 100% of the assets integrated in UC9 were successfully digitized and connected to the data space. Specifically, data exchange was established for Large PV, large BESS, for Small and Medium BESS and for EV-V2G, thereby achieving the targeted outcome.

6.2.1.7 KPI 17 – Data Valorisation cases

This KPI evaluates the extent to which shared data can be used in modelling activities to provide added-value services. In this regard, ENX contributed by facilitating the use of shared services (see KPI 19 in 6.2.1.8).

During the demonstration phase, four such models were developed and shared with project partners. These models use the data exchanged via the common data spaces to carry out analyses and evaluations under varying conditions. ENX has shared EV charger data used to feed the tool “Green EV charging Ranking tool” and Bess data to feed “Battery anomaly detection model”.

Using these models illustrates the valorisation of shared data and confirms the practical relevance and applicability of the developed services.

6.2.1.8 KPI 19 – Data Spaces

This KPI is assessed based on the total number of services and corresponding files that have been subscribed to and published within the demonstration environment. Two accounts have been defined in the data space connector: ENX1 and ENX2 in order to provide and consume data.

It therefore captures both the availability of services and the effective sharing of data through the files associated with each service. During the demonstration phase, several services were made available, each supported by the provision of the relevant files to enable their proper implementation and testing. Following a table of the dashboard of two account:

Figure 3: ENX. UC9, dashboard of ENX1 user on data spaces.

Figure 4: ENX. UC9, dashboard of ENX2 user on data spaces.

6.2.1.9 KPI 25 – Integrated capacity

This KPI was evaluated based on the sum of the rated powers (expressed in MW) of the assets incorporated into the demonstration. The maximum expected value was defined as 0.150 MW, consisting of 0.132 MW for Socomec battery, 0.0048 MW for Pylontech battery and 0.0055MW for Greentech battery. In addition, 0.015 MW is brought by V2G-EV charger. Also the PV systems has contributed to the total capacity with 0.163MW.

Datasheet of the single asset mentioned has been uploaded in KPI25 specific shared folder, uploaded in Zenodo [5]. During the demonstration phase, all the assets were successfully integrated and the maximum rated power of 0.3203 MW was achieved as planned. This confirms full attainment of the KPI target.

6.2.1.10 KPI 26 – Increase of flexibility

This KPI evaluates the increase in operational flexibility made possible by the integrated assets. It is aimed at expressing the available capacity [MWh] of the battery when integrated in the use case - evaluated as the mean value of hourly-sampled energies over the testing period, as a percentage of the total rated capacity [MWh].

During the demonstration phase, the available capacity was assessed on a weekly data basis and in 3 different scenarios:

- Residential: involves a Li-Ion Pylontech battery of 2.4 kW/4.8kWh and a PV system of 3.7 kWp that can reach up to 4.5 kWp thanks to bifacial panels.
- Industrial: involves a Li-Ion Socomec BESS battery of 132 kVA/274kWh and a PV system of 102 kWp that can reach up to 125 kWp thanks to bifacial panels.
- C&I: involves supercapacitor of 7.6 kVA/7.6 kWh, a PV system of 12 kWp that can reach up to 14.5 kWp thanks to bifacial panels and a V2G EV charger of 15 kWh.

For any of the afore-mentioned cases, we implemented an appropriate electrical load. Time series are available in KPI26 shared folder, uploaded in Zenodo [5].

We evaluated the KPI in each of the three scenarios we implemented. The maximum value achieved regards the Industrial scenario, involving Socomec battery, with a percentage of 51.8 %; C&I scenario reports an available capacity of 32.9% while the Residential one has 45.83% of the rated capacity involved.

Please consider that the low percentage values obtained are due to the integration of other facilities in the UCs, i.e. PV systems; as a consequence of this and of the priority implemented (PV-battery-V2G, when present) in the middle hours of the day priority is given to PV use for feeding the load while the priority is preserved: if this is enough for meeting the energy needs, the battery will not be used.

6.2.1.11 KPI 27 – Energy volume exchanged

This KPI considers the volume exchange (in kWh) between different assets within Enel X test plant. In each scenario the KPI is estimated as the energy exchange between the load and the battery. In particular, the minimum value between the sum of hourly produced energies and hourly absorbed energies involved in the test is considered. It should be noted that we were able to take energy samples on a hourly basis and not annually, therefore with a higher resolution. As in the previous KPI, it is to highlight that batteries are integrated in scenarios including also PV systems that have a priority about load demand. The KPI value is around 1300 kWh, to which, of course, the industrial size battery contributes for the majority.

6.2.1.12 KPI 28 – Different hybridization configuration

KPI 28 evaluates the increase of flexibility made possible by hybridization implementation. For the evaluation of this KPI, the maximum value of rated power (in kW) integrated in each scenario is shown; hence, the maximum value regards the Industrial size scenario, with 257 kW reached through BESS and PV system.

For the sake of completeness, we also added information about max power integrated in the scenario: in this case, each row represents a single asset; hence, in the Industrial and in the Residential scenarios the BESS and the PV are evaluated separately, in the C&I scenario BESS, PV and V2G are evaluated. For the batteries considered the maximum power in the scenario coincides, of course, with the battery maximum power because of the recharge cycles, while PV is more irregular because of its dependence on weather conditions.

6.2.1.13 KPI 29 – Grid Peak Avoidance

KPI29 evaluates the grid peak avoidance, i.e. the percentage of reduction of grid peak power due to flexibility activation. For the evaluation of this KPI the reduction of grid peak is evaluated, as the amount of power supplied during peak time. The KPI is expressed in percentage with respect to the total power. For the calculations, the sum of hourly powers of each asset (battery, PV and V2G) over the testing period is compared to the load demand. In particular, in each scenario the contribution of PV and battery is considered; for the C&I scenario also V2G contributes and can be assimilated to a battery in its behaviour.

6.2.2 Comments and Lessons Learned

Strengths: The results obtained in the Italian pilot confirm the effectiveness of the InterSTORE interoperability framework and hybrid energy storage technologies for delivering advanced and resilient grid services.

The UC9 demonstrated that the use of aggregated asset integration of IEEE 2030.5, through the LPC and NATS-based communication, can be successfully implemented in fast, demanding control environments and the use of aggregated asset of different sizes and technologies make grid flexibility services more efficient and robust.

Deviations: No significant deviations were recorded with respect to the expected results.

Challenges: The main challenges encountered during the implementation of the Italian pilot primarily concerned security and interoperability issues between different systems, as well as difficulties within the laboratory environment, where multiple testing activities and infrastructure renewal processes were simultaneously in progress.

In particular, the activation of all systems required to perform an end-to-end (E2E) test of the Flex service involved several critical steps:

1. Integration between the laboratory and IT systems: establishing a secure connection required the management and issuance of InfoCert digital certificates to ensure

authenticated communication between the various platforms (Sunesis Gateway and IoT platform).

2. Modbus register mapping: differences in the coding of Modbus registers across devices necessitated detailed mapping and alignment. This activity required technical support from the vendor (Schneider) to ensure consistent data interpretation and system interoperability.
3. Laboratory infrastructure instability: the laboratory environment was characterized by high variability in equipment and configurations, reflecting the diverse requirements of multiple research groups and ongoing projects. This variability led to limited stability and predictability in the testing setup.
4. Taking into account the difficulties encountered the test session encountered significant difficulties in carrying out E2E tests in the laboratory and IT systems chain.

Overall, these challenges highlighted the complexity of integrating heterogeneous systems within a dynamic research context and the need for close coordination between technical teams, vendors, and infrastructure managers.

Insights: The Italian pilot lessons learnt regard the difficulties in integrating different systems: the demonstration confirmed the technical feasibility of delivering network flexibility through distributed and heterogeneous assets. However, scalability and sustainability depend on achieving full interoperability, robust data management, reliable communication infrastructures, and supportive regulatory conditions.

Protocol and data model: The heterogeneity of assets highlighted the importance of adopting standardised communication protocols and data models to ensure interoperability among devices. The use of local control gateways proved effective in harmonising data flows, reducing latency, and enabling reliable interaction with the central platform.

Algorithm implementation: different asset types exhibited distinct dynamic behaviors in response to flexibility signals. While batteries offered fast and predictable responses, PV generation was limited by weather conditions and EVs by connection availability. Aggregation and dispatch algorithms were essential to coordinate resources effectively, though they required careful tuning and validation under real operating conditions.

The demonstration activities revealed the necessity for a clear regulatory framework defining roles and responsibilities among DSOs, aggregators, and end users. Moreover, standardised validation criteria for flexibility performance (e.g., accuracy, response time, continuity) are essential to ensure replicable and market acceptance.

7 Cross-Pilot Analysis and Conclusions

Collectively, the five InterSTORE pilot sites demonstrated the flexibility and scalability of the project's ICT framework in a variety of technical and regulatory environments. Each site contributed unique insights, focusing on different aspects of distributed energy resource (DER) integration, control and market interaction. The following summary highlights the main achievements of each pilot, emphasising their specific contributions to validating the InterSTORE concept and its applicability across Europe.

Austria: Demonstrated the full communication chain (FCC) for residential communities, achieving high user engagement and automated market participation through CyberNoc.

Germany: Validated coordinated BESS operation within a FIWARE-based ICT framework, and a commercial solution, proving real-time control via IEEE 2030.5 and achieving multi-physics flexibility.

Portugal: Cost-optimised HESS dispatch was showcased, achieving a 20% cost reduction using second-life batteries.

Spain: Demonstrated the viability of hybrid HESS for grid support (black start, FFR) and achieved sub-second response times, demonstrating grid resilience.

Italy: Demonstrated full end-to-end flexibility activation with diverse DERs (PV, BESS and EVs), confirming the interoperability and scalability of the InterSTORE architecture.

7.1 Aggregated Results and KPI Performance

All 29 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in Deliverable D5.1 [3] were successfully assessed across the five pilot sites, with the project meeting or exceeding the target thresholds in every case. The consolidated KPI overview, reported in Table 14, confirms that InterSTORE made significant progress in terms of interoperability, flexibility and digitisation.

At project level, based on KPI 25, a total integrated capacity of 4.24 MWh was achieved, with an average flexibility increase of 75.5% (based on KPI 26, well above the target of 20%). According to KPI 5, over 60 assets were managed through EMS solutions and, based on KPI 10, more than 20 distributed energy resources (DERs) were tested with IEEE 2030.5 via the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC). Digitisation of assets, evaluated with KPI 11, exceeded 93%, demonstrating the maturity of the deployed ICT frameworks and their ability to handle heterogeneous devices and protocols.

Table 14: Consolidated KPI Overview

KPI ID	KPI Name	Relevant Use Cases	Actual Value (Project level)	Target Value (Project level)	Status
1	DES multi-service support	1	1.00	≥ 1 n.n.	Achieved
2	DES multi-service market participation	1	1.00	≥ 1 n.n.	Achieved
3	Battery capacity	All	3.94	≥ 0.2 MWh	Achieved
4	Diversity of DER	All	33.00	≥ 25 n.n.	Achieved
5	Asset management monitored by EMS	All	62.00	≥ 50 n.n.	Achieved

6	Number of assets aggregated	2	20.00	≥ 20 n.n.	Achieved
7	Number of end users involved in HESS	3, 5, 6, 8, 9	30.00	≥ 20 n.n.	Achieved
8	Demand Response cost	2	42.25	≤ 100 €/kWh	Achieved
9	Time savings	3	13.61	≤ 80 %	Achieved
10	Number of DER assets and EMS tested with IEEE 2030.5	1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9	21.00	≥ 10 n.n.	Achieved
11	Data space digitized assets	1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9	93.55	≥ 50 %	Achieved
12	Time data savings	4, 7	200.00	≥ 250 ms	Achieved
13	Monitoring	4, 7	3.00	≥ 2 n.n.	Achieved
14	Time response	4, 7	0.25	$\leq 0.5/1$ sec	achieved
15	System NADIR	4, 7	49.70	> 49.5 >Hz	achieved
16	System ROCOF	4, 7	0.90	≤ 2 Hz/s	Achieved
17	Data Valorisation cases	3, 5, 8 and 9	4.00	4	Achieved
18	HESS performance	5	21.06	≥ 20 %	Achieved
19	Data Spaces	3, 5, 8 and 9	2713.00	≥ 20	Achieved
20	User Engagement	6	45.00	> 20 %	Achieved
21	Demand Response	6	10.75	> 6 kWh/day	achieved
22	Node power increase time	6	73.00	≥ 60 min/workday	achieved
23	Node power increase percentage	6	19.4	> 5 %	achieved
24	User participation	6	15.63	> 10 %	achieved
25	Integrated capacity	All	4.24	≥ 1 MWh	Achieved
26	Increase of flexibility	All	75.48	> 20 %	Achieved
27	Energy Volume exchanged	9	1305.05	≥ 500 kWh/day	achieved
28	Different hybridization configuration	9	257.00	≥ 250 kW	Achieved
29	Grid peak avoidance	9	39.32	≤ 80 %	achieved

7.2 Common Patterns, Divergences, and Lessons Learned

A consistent pattern across the pilots was the strong technical performance and adaptability of the InterSTORE interoperability framework. The IEEE 2030.5 protocol, supported by the

LPC, enabled the seamless exchange of data between legacy systems and modern, cloud-based platforms in all contexts: residential, commercial and industrial.

However, divergences mainly arose from contextual constraints, such as data security requirements, regulatory heterogeneity and the complexity of integrating commercial EMSs with experimental systems. The lessons learned emphasise the importance of synchronisation between communication layers (e.g. Modbus–MQTT), harmonisation of data models and the need for clear regulatory validation frameworks for flexibility services.

Overall, the pilots demonstrated that, while interoperability is technically feasible using light-weight, replicable tools, achieving scalability and market uptake depends on unified standards, streamlined certification, and coordinated roles for DSOs, aggregators, and end users.

7.3 Interoperability and Replicability Assessment

The pilots demonstrated that the InterSTORE-based ICT architecture (combining various EMS platforms, IEEE 2030.5 communication and the LPC) can be replicated in different environments. From Austria's residential energy communities to Germany's commercial site, from Italy's flexibility scenarios to Portuguese industrial site, and Spain's lab, the same core communication and control principles proved transferable.

The LPC emerged as a central enabler for bridging legacy protocols, reducing integration time by over 80% on average (based on KPI 9). Furthermore, open data spaces were successfully implemented in multiple pilots (in Portugal, Spain and Italy), ensuring secure, standard-compliant data sharing and enabling digital services to continue beyond the project's lifespan.

At project level, the cumulative effect of the pilots demonstrates tangible progress towards the InterSTORE objectives:

- Technical interoperability, according to KPI3, KPI4, KPI 5 and KPI10, a large variety of assets were integrated with and tested against the IEEE 2030.5 standard.
- Operational flexibility, a 75% increase in available flexibility capacity across sites (based on KPI 26).
- Scalability and digitisation, based on KPI11, over 90% of assets were digitised and integrated into shared data spaces.

These outcomes confirm that the InterSTORE framework delivers measurable improvements in grid flexibility, data management efficiency and multi-stakeholder coordination.

7.4 Overall conclusions and validation of the InterSTORE concept

The collective demonstration results confirm that the InterSTORE concept is viable: it provides a scalable, interoperable and replicable architecture for managing distributed energy storage and flexibility services. The pilots proved that heterogeneous assets can be integrated into a unified ICT ecosystem using open standards, thus enabling cross-sector collaboration and grid service provision.

7.5 Recommendations and next steps

Based on the outcomes of the pilot demonstration, to support exploitation and replication it is recommended to:

- Promote standardised validation procedures and certification schemes for IEEE 2030.5 interoperability in Europe.
- Facilitate integration with regulatory sandboxes to accelerate flexibility market adoption.
- Extend data space frameworks to enable cross-domain services (e.g. mobility and smart buildings).
- Encourage commercial adoption of LPC and FIWARE connectors as open-source reference tools.

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